

Report on Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Global Entrepreneurship Monitor

Ukraine 2024 / 2025

Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Ukraine 2024/2025

National Report

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Sponsors

The research was organized as part of the Good Governance Fund project "Inclusive Economy", funded by UK International Development from the UK government. The project implementer is Abt Global.

Published

10.10.2025

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Preview

The Entrepreneurship Ecosystem Report of Ukraine 2024/2025 is the second study conducted using the GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor) methodology.

Ukraine's accession to GEM in 2023 became a significant event amid the crisis conditions for entrepreneurship caused by the war that began in February 2022.

Ukraine's participation in the GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR project in 2023 became possible thanks to the sponsorship support of the School of Management Fribourg (HEG-FR) (Switzerland) and the Institute for Circular and Hydrogen Economy (Ukraine).

In 2024, Ukraine's participation is carried out within the framework of the Good Governance Fund "Inclusive Economy" project, financed by UK International Development from the Government of the United Kingdom. The project implementer is Abt Global. Thanks to this support, the national team conducted a new study — GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR Ukraine 2024/2025.

The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), launched as a pilot program in 1998 by the London Business School and Babson College, is considered the most comprehensive and long-running study of entrepreneurship in the world. Over its 25 years of existence, GEM has repeatedly provided policymakers with valuable insights into how to shape entrepreneurial ecosystems to foster growth and societal prosperity.

The GEM global research consortium measures entrepreneurial activity across many countries and has recorded over 140,000 unique downloads, with its website generating around 1 million page views annually. The authors of the Global Report are an expert group of entrepreneurship researchers within the global GEM consortium, consisting of about 400 researchers. Around 60 national GEM teams will participate in the Global Report 2024/2025. For Ukraine, this partnership provides access to the results of global business research and is crucial for understanding global trends and making comparisons with other economies.

This year's study presents data on entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine under the conditions of the full-scale war, now in its third year. The Adult Population Survey results provide important information on the positive social perception of entrepreneurs, motivation to start a business during crisis conditions, fear of failure as a barrier, levels of business activity, and perceptions of future opportunities. The topic of business digitalization is highly relevant for global economies and has been duly reflected in this report.

The Adult Population Survey also included new topics particularly relevant to Ukraine — the challenges and specific experiences of entrepreneurs from vulnerable groups, including war veterans, people with disabilities, and internally displaced persons (IDPs). The purpose of this part of the study was to identify the problems and needs of veteran entrepreneurs, entrepreneurs with disabilities, and IDP entrepreneurs. These findings are of great importance for potential stakeholders.

The Government of Ukraine, state institutions, and other interested parties have an urgent need for reliable and unbiased data to make key decisions that will stimulate adaptive forms of entrepreneurial ecosystem development under wartime conditions.

Special sections of the report provide information on gender aspects of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem. Women's activity in starting new businesses, their ability to adapt in crisis conditions, access to finance, and the regulatory and tax environment — these and other aspects form the basis for an expert assessment of the country's business environment.

Передмова

Звіт про екосистему підприємництва України 2024/2025 – це друге дослідження, яке проводиться за методологією GEM. Приєднання національної команди України до GEM у 2023 році стало важливою подією в кризових умовах підприємницької діяльності, з якими країна стикнулася внаслідок війни, що розпочалася у лютому 2022 року.

Залучення України в 2023 році до проєкту GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR стало можливим завдяки спонсорській підтримці Фрібурзької школи менеджменту (HEG-FR) (Швейцарія) та Інституту циркулярної та водневої економіки (Україна).

У 2024 році участь України здійснюється у рамках проєкту Good Governance Fund «Інклюзивна економіка», який фінансується UK International Development від уряду Великої Британії. Імплементатор проєкту – Abt Global. Завдяки цьому національна команда виконала нове дослідження: GLOBAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP MONITOR Ukraine 2024/2025.

Глобальний моніторинг підприємництва (GEM), який був започаткований у якості пілотної програми в 1998 році Лондонською школою бізнесу і Бебсон-коледжем, вважається найбільш повним і довготривалим дослідженням підприємництва у всьому світі. Протягом 25 років існування GEM неодноразово надавав політикам цінну інформацію про те, як формувати екосистему підприємництва, щоб сприяти зростанню та процвітанню суспільства.

Глобальний дослідницький консорціум GEM проводить вимірювання підприємницької діяльності в багатьох країнах і містить понад 140 000 унікальних завантажень, веб-сайт GEM генерує близько 1 мільйона переглядів сторінок щороку. Авторами Глобального звіту є експертна група дослідників підприємництва глобального консорціуму GEM, що складається з близько 400 дослідників. Близько 60 національних команд GEM братимуть участь у Глобальному звіті 2024/2025. Для України це партнерство надає доступ до результатів глобальних бізнес-досліджень і має вирішальне значення для розуміння світових тенденцій та порівняння з іншими економіками.

Цьогорічне дослідження представляє дані про підприємницьку діяльність в Україні в умовах повномасштабної війни, яка триває третій рік. Результати опитування дорослого населення містять важливу інформацію про позитивне суспільне сприйняття підприємців, бажання та мотивацію почати бізнес в кризових умовах, страх невдачі як перешкоди, рівень ділової активності та бачення перспектив розвитку. Тема цифровізації бізнесу є актуальною для світових економік і належним чином врахована в нашому звіті.

В опитуванні дорослого населення досліджувалися нові теми, які є актуальними саме для України, зокрема, виклики та особливості діяльності підприємців для уразливих груп - ветеранів війни, осіб з інвалідністю, внутрішньо переміщених осіб. Метою дослідження було визначення проблем та потреб ветеранів (-ок), підприємців(-ць) з інвалідністю, підприємців(-ць) внутрішньо переміщених осіб.

Ці дослідження важливі для потенційних стейкхолдерів. Уряд України, державні інституції та інші зацікавлені сторони мають нагальну потребу у достовірних та неупереджених даних для прийняття ключових рішень, які стимулюють адаптивні форми розвитку підприємницької екосистеми в умовах війни. Спеціальні розділи звіту містять інформацію про гендерні аспекти підприємницької екосистеми України. Активність жінок у відкритті нового бізнесу, їх здатність до адаптації в кризових умовах, доступ на фінансування, нормативно-правові та податкові умови бізнесу ці та інші аспекти є основою для експертної оцінки бізнес-середовища країни.

Key findings and recommendations

Key findings

Key Findings of the Comprehensive Report on the Application of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) in Ukraine. The report, combined with expert conclusions and statistical analysis, provides a detailed overview of the entrepreneurial landscape in challenging conditions:

Entrepreneurial Activity and Resilience

Despite the war, Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem demonstrates resilience. Total Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) reached 19.9%, reflecting a strong entrepreneurial spirit among Ukrainians. However, entrepreneurial activity intensity varies significantly by region. Central and northern regions exhibit higher TEA rates, while southern and eastern regions, most affected by the war, face substantial barriers to business development.

National Entrepreneurial Context

The National Entrepreneurial Context Index (NECI) in Ukraine is rated at 4.38, classified as a "moderate" level. Positive changes are noted in government programs and entrepreneurship financing. However, challenges persist in physical infrastructure and socio-cultural norms, which complicate entrepreneurial efforts. Additionally, the war has exacerbated pre-existing issues in fiscal policy, business financing, and the adoption of scientific advancements. A high level of entrepreneurial education and widespread public recognition of the importance of entrepreneurship provide a solid foundation for addressing these challenges.

Comparative Analysis with Neighboring Countries

Despite the war, Ukraine's NECI is on par with Poland and Romania (4.3), surpassing Slovakia (4.0). The only neighboring country with a higher score is Hungary (4.5). These findings highlight the resilience of Ukraine's economy and its capacity to compete on the international stage.

Social Views and Gender Perspectives

Ukrainian society exhibits a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship, particularly among women, who view business as a promising career opportunity more optimistically. However, gender gaps in confidence and perceptions of success require additional efforts to support women in business. Key barriers include fear of failure, cultural norms, and limited access to resources.

Landscape of Informal Investment

Informal investment remains a critical source of support for entrepreneurs, primarily directed toward businesses of family members, friends, or acquaintances. The gender gap in this area highlights the need to engage women in investment activities and ensure equal access to financial resources.

Innovation and Digitalization

Despite challenges, Ukrainian entrepreneurs are actively implementing innovations. In northern regions, 52.7% of entrepreneurs plan to adopt new technologies. The use of modern tools such as cloud technologies, data analytics, and artificial intelligence is increasing. However, innovation activities are mostly local in scope, and their impact on the business ecosystem remains limited.

Main Recommendations

Ukraine's strategy to improve its entrepreneurial ecosystem in times of war and beyond should be comprehensive and multi-level.

Combating Corruption and Ensuring Transparency:

Amid war, it is critically important to ensure effective oversight of resources and the allocation of financial aid. Implementing anti-corruption measures will enhance investor confidence and create a transparent business environment.

Financial Support for Entrepreneurs:

Introduce financial mechanisms for targeted support to vulnerable populations, including direct funding, access to low-interest loans, and crisis management training. These measures will help entrepreneurs remain resilient during the war and recover operations in the post-war period.

Encouraging Innovation and Digital Technologies:

Provide entrepreneurs with access to digital tools and digital literacy training. Support the development of new products, services, and the adoption of technologies through grants and government programs.

Gender Equality in Entrepreneurship:

Develop specialized programs to support women in business. Introduce mentorship, networking initiatives, and simplified access to financing for women entrepreneurs.

Infrastructure Development:

Invest in upgrading physical and technological infrastructure critical to supporting businesses. Provide support to displaced businesses for adaptation to new conditions and create incentives for their return after the war.

Expanding International Partnerships:

Actively develop international cooperation, attract foreign investors, and participate in business forums. Expanding exports and access to international markets will ensure economic growth and stability.

The GEM report on Ukraine provides a clear picture of the entrepreneurial ecosystem during wartime. Despite significant challenges, Ukraine demonstrates the potential for gradual economic growth due to international support, business adaptation, and measures aimed at macro-financial stability. However, to develop effective strategies, it is essential to systematically monitor the dynamics of the situation. Regular reporting is necessary to understand trends and respond promptly, fostering favorable conditions for the development and prosperity of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Основні висновки та рекомендації

Основні висновки

Основні висновки комплексного звіту про застосування Глобального моніторингу підприємництва (GEM) в Україні разом із експертними висновками та статистичним аналізом дають детальну картину підприємницького ландшафту в складних умовах:

Підприємницька активність та стійкість

Незважаючи на війну, підприємницька екосистема України демонструє стійкість. Загальна підприємницька активність (ТЕА) досягла 19,9%, що свідчить про сильний дух підприємництва серед українців. Однак, інтенсивність підприємницької діяльності значно варіюється залежно від регіону. Центральні та північні області показують вищі показники ТЕА, тоді як південні та східні регіони, які найбільше постраждали від війни, мають суттєві обмеження для розвитку бізнесу.

Національне підприємницьке середовище

Національний контекст підприємництва (NECI) в Україні оцінено на рівні 4.38, що класифікується як «середній» показник. Позитивні зміни є в державних програмах та кредитуванні підприємництва. Проблемними сторонами є фізична інфраструктура та соціальні і культурні норми, які ускладнюють умови підприємницької діяльності. Водночас війна посилила існуючі проблеми в сфері фіскальної політики, фінансування бізнесу та впровадження наукових розробок. Високий рівень підприємницької освіти та визнання значущості підприємництва серед населення є потенціалом для подолання цих викликів.

Порівняльний аналіз із сусідніми країнами:

Незважаючи на війну, NECI України знаходиться на рівні Польщі та Румунії (4.3), випереджаючи Словаччину (4.0). Єдиною країною-сусідом з вищим показником є Угорщина (4.5). Ці дані свідчать про стійкість української економіки та її здатність змагатися на міжнародній арені.

Соціальні погляди та гендерні перспективи:

Українське суспільство демонструє позитивне ставлення до підприємництва, зокрема серед жінок, які більш оптимістично оцінюють бізнес як кар'єрну можливість. Водночас гендерний розрив у самовпевненості та сприйнятті успіху вимагає додаткових зусиль для підтримки жінок у бізнесі. Серед основних бар'єрів – страх невдачі, культурні норми та брак доступу до ресурсів.

Ландшафт неформального інвестування:

Неформальне інвестування залишається важливим джерелом підтримки для підприємців. Воно найчастіше спрямовується на підтримку бізнесів членів родини, друзів або знайомих. Гендерний розрив у цій сфері свідчить про необхідність залучення жінок до участі в інвестиційній діяльності та забезпечення рівності у доступі до фінансів.

Інновації та цифровізація:

Попри виклики, підприємці України активно впроваджують інновації. У північних регіонах 52,7% підприємців планують застосування нових технологій. Використання сучасних інструментів, таких як хмарні технології, аналіз даних та штучний інтелект, зростає. Водночас інноваційна діяльність здебільшого має локальний характер, а її вплив на екосистему бізнесу поки залишається обмеженим.

Рекомендації

Стратегія України щодо покращення підприємницької екосистеми під час та після війни має бути комплексною та багаторівневою.

Боротьба з корупцією та прозорість:

В умовах війни критично важливо забезпечити ефективний контроль над ресурсами та розподілом фінансової допомоги. Реалізувати антикорупційні заходи, які підвищать довіру інвесторів та створять прозоре бізнес-середовище.

Фінансова підтримка підприємців:

Запровадити фінансові механізми адресної підтримки вразливих груп населення, які включають пряме фінансування, доступ до кредитів із пільговими умовами, навчання кризовому управлінню. Це допоможе підприємцям зберігати стійкість під час війни та відновлювати діяльність у післявоєнний період.

Стимулювання інновацій та цифрових технологій:

Забезпечити підприємцям доступ до цифрових інструментів і навчання цифровій грамотності. Підтримувати розробку нових продуктів, послуг і впровадження технологій через гранти та державні програми.

Гендерна рівність у підприємництві:

Розробити спеціалізовані програми для підтримки жінок у бізнесі. Впровадити менторство, мережеві ініціативи, а також спрощений доступ до фінансування для жінок-підприємниць.

Розвиток інфраструктури:

Інвестувати в оновлення фізичної та технологічної інфраструктури, необхідної для підтримки підприємств. Надати підтримку переміщеним бізнесам для їх адаптації в нових умовах і створити стимули для їх повернення після війни.

Розширення міжнародного партнерства:

Активно розвивати міжнародне співробітництво, залучати іноземних інвесторів, брати участь у бізнес-форумах. Розширення експорту та доступ до міжнародних ринків забезпечить економічне зростання та стабільність.

Звіт GEM про Україну надав чітку картину стану підприємницької екосистеми в умовах війни. Незважаючи на серйозні виклики, Україна демонструє потенціал до поступового економічного зростання завдяки міжнародній підтримці, адаптації бізнесу та заходам, спрямованим на макрофінансову стабільність. Проте, для розробки ефективних стратегій потрібно систематично відстежувати динаміку ситуації, тому необхідно проводити регулярні звіти, які допоможуть розуміти тенденції і вчасно реагувати на них, сприяючи створенню сприятливих умов для розвитку та процвітання підприємницької екосистеми в Україні.

1. The methodology of GEM and its application in Ukraine

The network consortium of national teams from various countries, guided by the GEM principles of values (Integrity, Innovation, Distinction), utilizes a unique research methodology on entrepreneurship and produces reports for diverse stakeholder groups.

The **Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM)** employs a long-standing methodology that ensures comprehensive and adaptive research and evaluation of entrepreneurial ecosystems worldwide. GEM data covers the characteristics, motivations, ambitions, and societal attitudes of entrepreneurs, taking into account the state of national ecosystems and global challenges. The core tools of this methodology are the **Adult Population Survey (APS)** and the **National Expert Survey (NES)**.

The **Adult Population Survey (APS)**, targeting individuals aged 18 to 64, focuses on studying the scale and nature of entrepreneurial activity, including those actively engaged in planning, starting, or running a business. This survey also examines societal attitudes towards entrepreneurship and the motivational features of different categories of entrepreneurs. To ensure representativeness, GEM collects data from at least 2,000 respondents in each surveyed economy. In 2024, a survey of 2,012 respondents was conducted in Ukraine.

The **National Expert Survey (NES)** aims to assess the impact of external environments and infrastructure conditions on entrepreneurial activity. NES involves surveying professionals from various fields, including finance, public policy, education, research, and market analysis. According to GEM methodology, a minimum of 36 experts is required. The expert evaluation of factors promoting and barriers hindering entrepreneurial activity provides impartial information about critical aspects of the national entrepreneurial environment and is used to formulate recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders.

In 2024, the national team, in partnership with the **Federation of Employers of Ukraine** and the **Institute of Circular and Hydrogen Economy (ICHE)**, engaged 58 experts for the NES survey.

The **National Expert Survey (NES)** was conducted online in the summer of 2024. The survey covered a wide range of topics, including financial accessibility and government support, facilitating the analysis of the entrepreneurial infrastructure of Ukraine's economy. The study's outcome was the development of the **National Entrepreneurship Context Index (NECI)**, a valuable tool for entrepreneurs and policymakers, enabling comparisons of entrepreneurial support and facilitation across different economies.

Classifiers are an essential component of the GEM methodology. When conducting entrepreneurship research worldwide, it is crucial to consider the socio-political context of a country and its level of economic development compared to other nations.

The GEM reports use a country classification system based on GDP per capita, according to estimates by the World Bank, which prepares annual reports. This categorization helps provide a structured analysis of countries' economic development and incorporate this factor into the formation of conclusions.

The GEM methodology is flexible and adapts to global changes and needs. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, GEM added new questions to its survey to analyze its economic impact. Moreover, in 2021, GEM expanded its survey to include questions about environmental issues

and corporate social responsibility. In subsequent years, these research aspects were further developed to incorporate awareness of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Special surveys on the development of national ecosystems are another key feature of the GEM methodology. Each national team has the opportunity to include additional questions to identify current factors influencing entrepreneurial activity.

In the 2023 GEM report, countries are classified into three groups based on GDP per capita, using World Bank estimates (see Table 1.1). This classification serves to structure the data and improve comparability within and between groups. The participation of 60 national teams in the 2024 study demonstrates the broad range of economies covered by GEM.

Table 1.1 Economies in GEM 2023, categorized by income group (GDP/cap)

Level A	Level B	Level C
>\$50,000	\$25,000–\$50,000	<\$25,000
Canada	Argentina*	Brazil
France	Chile	China
Germany	Croatia	Colombia
Italy	Cyprus	Ecuador
Rep. Korea	Estonia	Guatemala
Luxembourg	Greece	India
Netherlands	Hungary	Iran
Norway	Israel	Jordan
Qatar	Japan	Mexico
Saudi Arabia	Latvia	Morocco
Slovenia	Lithuania	South Africa
Sweden	Oman	Thailand
Switzerland	Panama	Ukraine
United Arab Emirates	Poland	Venezuela
United Kingdom	Puerto Rico	
United States	Romania	
	Slovak Republic	
	Spain	
	Uruguay	

Source: Global Report, 25 Years and Growing

The first group (level A) comprises countries with a GDP per capita of more than USD 50,000, including developed economies such as the United States, Germany and Switzerland. The second group (level B) consists of countries whose GDP per capita is between USD 25,000 and USD 50,000, including both developed countries such as Japan and Spain and developing countries such as Poland, Oman and Panama. The third group (level C) comprises countries with a GDP per capita of less than USD 25,000, including mainly developing countries and lower-income countries such as India, Morocco, Venezuela and Brazil.

Both the GSP and the NES are conducted annually in each participating country. The GEM teams provide policy makers with access to up-to-date information on entrepreneurship so that they can make informed decisions to promote the development of a successful and quality entrepreneurial environment in their countries. The data collected through these surveys is analysed with the aim of producing national and global reports that play a crucial role in shaping entrepreneurship policy and research.

The first group (Level A) includes countries with a GDP per capita exceeding \$50,000, encompassing developed economies such as the United States, Germany, and Switzerland. The second group (Level B) consists of countries with a GDP per capita ranging from \$25,000 to \$50,000, including both developed countries like Japan and Spain and developing countries such as Poland, Oman, and Panama. The third group (Level C) includes countries with a GDP per capita of less than \$25,000, primarily consisting of developing and low-income countries such as India, Morocco, Venezuela, and Brazil.

The Global GEM Report also features the GEM National Entrepreneurship Context Index (NECI), which evaluates the entrepreneurial context of a specific economy. The results are based on scores provided by national experts on the set of Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions for each GEM-participating country in a given year. The index serves as an invaluable tool for comparing entrepreneurial ecosystems at both regional and global levels.

1.1. Demographic and socio-economic profile of Ukrainian APS respondents in 2024

From August to September, a survey of the adult population was conducted in Ukraine using the GEM methodology, resulting in the collection of 2012 responses.

The 2023 survey data were relatively balanced regarding the gender distribution of the Adult Population Survey (APS) participants (48% men and 52% women). However, in 2024, a higher proportion of women (70%) participated compared to men (30%) (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Profile of respondents in Ukraine by gender, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The impact of the war on the distribution of APS survey participants, as well as on the content and nature of the surveys, is profound and multifaceted. Many men are serving in the military, which significantly reduces their participation in sociological surveys. During active warfare, men in combat zones often lack access to survey platforms and the time needed to participate. Women, on the other hand, are assuming greater societal and family responsibilities on the home front, making them key respondents in sociological research.

By age category, the dynamics of respondents between 2023 and 2024 remained almost unchanged (Figure 1.2). The largest group of respondents belongs to the 25–34 age group (27%), while the smallest group is in the 18–24 age range (13%) (Figure 1.2). The vast majority of respondents are either fully or partially employed, including self-employed individuals, who make up 62% of the survey participants. A smaller but significant portion of respondents are

currently salaried employees (16%), while others fall into categories such as "retiree," "homemaker," "student," or "unemployed."

Figure 1.2. Profile of respondents in Ukraine by age category, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The results of the regional profile analysis of respondents for 2024 indicate a certain level of heterogeneity. Compared to 2023, the distribution of respondents in 2024 shows a decrease in participation in the Eastern (12.2%) and Southern (12.2%) regions. At the same time, the figures are relatively balanced across three regions: the Western region (26.9%), the Central region (23.6%), and the Northern region (24.8%) (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3. Profile of respondents by region, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The reasons for regional disparities in the Adult Population Survey can vary and depend on several factors. The decrease in the share of respondents from the Eastern and Southern regions may be linked to economic challenges or social circumstances, such as population migration from occupied territories. Regions closer to zones of instability may experience reduced entrepreneurial activity or difficulties in accessing surveyed entrepreneurs. People and businesses tend to relocate to more stable regions, such as the Western and Central ones, which influences the statistical base of the survey.

1.2. Profile of the Ukrainian NES participants at GEM 2024

The evaluation of the entrepreneurial economic system in Ukraine is largely shaped by the diverse expertise of its professionals, as highlighted in the National Expert Survey (NES) conducted by GEM Ukraine in 2024. The Ukrainian iteration of the NES saw significant participation, with 65 experts contributing to the survey. The gender distribution was nearly equal, with 51% men and 49% women taking part in the study (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4. Gender profile of respondents NES, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

An analysis of these experts' profiles, based on their professional experience, provides critical insights into the dynamics of Ukraine's business landscape and its growth potential. The majority of respondents possess extensive experience, with many having dedicated over ten years to entrepreneurial activities (Figure 1.5). Experts with long-standing careers in the field tend to foster an ecosystem characterized by mentorship, knowledge transfer, and collaboration.

Figure 1.5. Total years working in areas connected to entrepreneurship of respondents to the National Expert Survey (NES), 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Their historical perspective enables them to identify trends and shifts in the market, guiding young entrepreneurs through the complexities of starting and scaling businesses. This extensive exposure provides them with detailed insights into the challenges and opportunities in the Ukrainian market. The diverse range of expertise — from prominent business owners to academics — ensures a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial economic environment in Ukraine.

Additionally, considering the socio-political challenges Ukraine faces, including regulatory hurdles and market instability, the insights of these experts are invaluable. Their experience

often encompasses resilience, adaptability, and strategic thinking—qualities essential for evaluating an entrepreneurial landscape that is rapidly evolving and under the strain of ongoing military conflict.

The demographic distribution of experts reflects a mix of seasoned professionals and emerging thought leaders (Figure 1.6).

Figure 1.6. Profile of respondents by age category to the National Expert Survey (NES), 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Experts with many years of entrepreneurial experience bring invaluable perspectives shaped by practical knowledge, which is crucial for assessing and navigating the complexities of Ukraine's economy. Such experience fosters a deeper understanding of both the challenges and opportunities present in the market, as these professionals have witnessed shifts driven by regulatory changes, market demands, and socio-political factors.

Additionally, the education and specialization of NES respondents highlight a diverse range of skills and expertise that contribute to a well-informed evaluation of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem (Figures 1.7 and 1.8).

Figure 1.7. Profile of respondents by specialization of the National Expert Survey (NES), 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The accreditation of NES participants was particularly high: 55% had at least a higher education degree, while 45% held a master's or Ph.D. Such a level of academic achievement among respondents underscores their comprehensive understanding and ability to provide detailed insights into the development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine. The combination of diverse educational qualifications—from business administration to technical fields—facilitates a rich exchange of ideas and promotes collaboration, which can drive economic growth.

Figure 1.8. Profile of respondents by educational level of the National Expert Survey (NEO), 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

In conclusion, the profiles of experts analyzed in the NES not only illustrate the breadth of experience and education present in Ukrainian entrepreneurship but also highlight the importance of these factors in assessing the country’s business landscape. As Ukraine continues to navigate economic challenges, leveraging expert insights will play a crucial role in shaping sustainable entrepreneurial practices and fostering economic growth.

1.3.GEM in Ukraine: Methodology and Assessment

The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) in Ukraine serves as a comprehensive tool for assessing the country’s entrepreneurial landscape. In 2024, GEM in Ukraine incorporates several national aspects.

Firstly, the war has led to an increase in the number of individuals belonging to vulnerable population groups, including war veterans, people with disabilities, internally displaced persons (IDPs), and rural entrepreneurs. Consequently, in 2024, the Adult Population Survey (APS) included questions aimed at identifying the key motivations and needs of these vulnerable groups. Entrepreneurs and veterans often express the need for tailored assistance programs addressing their unique circumstances. Similarly, entrepreneurs with disabilities face systemic barriers, highlighting the need for strategies to promote inclusivity in business practices.

Domestically, the presence of formalized inclusivity policies is crucial for creating equitable workplaces. This focus on inclusivity not only supports vulnerable groups but also contributes to a more resilient and diversified entrepreneurial ecosystem in Ukraine.

Secondly, for internally displaced persons (IDPs), entrepreneurship represents a pathway to financial independence and self-realization. However, they require supportive infrastructure, mentorship, and access to financing to overcome the challenges associated with displacement.

Overall, creating an inclusive business environment necessitates comprehensive support for entrepreneurs, including training, financial resources, and opportunities for networking. Addressing these needs, GEM can provide valuable insights and help foster a more favorable entrepreneurial climate that embraces innovation and inclusivity across all sectors of Ukrainian society.

The entrepreneurial ecosystem faces unique challenges, particularly in rural areas, where access to resources and support networks remains limited. By identifying these gaps, targeted

interventions can help strengthen entrepreneurship in underserved regions, contributing to the resilience and growth of Ukraine’s economy.

Thirdly, Ukraine is actively implementing digitalization in business establishment and administration, creating modern tools to simplify these processes. In 2024, the Adult Population Survey (APS) included additional questions regarding the use of artificial intelligence tools and digital applications to enhance operational efficiency and decision-making.

The expected impacts of adopting artificial intelligence include improved customer interactions, optimized processes, and innovation-driven growth. GEM's methodology for evaluating the impact of digitalization on the entrepreneurial ecosystem provides valuable insights for policymakers, as Ukrainian entrepreneurs increasingly adopt these technologies, and reliance on digital solutions is expected to grow.

Moreover, the rise of digital technologies has encouraged more entrepreneurs to focus on IT, software development, and e-commerce, leveraging global trends and responding to local demand. This shift highlights the importance of digital literacy and innovation in driving Ukraine’s entrepreneurial growth and competitiveness.

2. Overview of the economic situation

In 2022, the Ukrainian economy faced unprecedented challenges due to the onset of war. The economic landscape for entrepreneurs became a space of instability and unpredictability, with supply chains disrupted and market stability undermined. However, despite these challenges, 2024 demonstrates the first signs of economic resilience and recovery, driven by government policies aimed at supporting and strengthening economic activity among the population.

Economic disparities in the development of Ukraine's regions have likely intensified during 2023–2024, revealing significant contrasts in wealth, infrastructure, and investment. The eastern and southern regions, traditionally reliant on heavy industry and agriculture, are struggling with the economic consequences of ongoing shelling and occupation, jeopardizing their recovery and growth. In contrast, the western regions of Ukraine have experienced more sustainable development due to foreign investments and the relocation of businesses.

One of the critical factors contributing to this disparity is the uneven distribution of resources and investments. Western Ukraine increasingly attracts international support and investments through efforts to align with European Union standards and practices. The migration of skilled labor from eastern to western regions further exacerbates the economic divide, reinforcing the challenges faced by the eastern and southern parts of the country while fostering growth in the west.

2.1.GDP

According to the National Bank of Ukraine (NBU), economic activity in 2024 is gradually recovering after the shock of the early weeks of the full-scale war. Businesses are adapting to the new conditions, and the percentage of enterprises that have completely ceased operations has decreased from over 30% in March 2024 to 23% by early April. At the same time, real GDP growth in the first quarter of 2024 remained modest due to budget constraints and the blockade of the western border [1]. The International Monetary Fund has confirmed its forecast for Ukraine's GDP growth at 4% this year and 2.5–3.5% next year, while predicting a significant improvement in this indicator in 2026–2027 (Figure 2.1).

Figure.2.1. Dynamics of Ukraine's GDP growth rates for the period 2021-2024

Source: National Bank of Ukraine (official website)¹

Business activity in Ukraine remains unstable throughout 2024. In December, business sentiment continued to decline, and economic activity slowed in several sectors due to the

¹ Source: National Bank of Ukraine (official website)

challenging energy and security situation, labor shortages, and difficulties in accessing financing.

Domestic demand—both consumer and investment—remained resilient, supporting retail trade and industrial production. Labor shortages remain significant, driving further wage growth. At the same time, the annual rate of wage increases accelerated, indicating continued growth in both the supply and demand for labor.

2.2. Inflation

The entrepreneurial ecosystem is highly sensitive to crises and global challenges. A key indicator of the economy's health is the dynamics of prices for goods and services. In Ukraine, inflation is on the rise (Fig. 2.2), primarily driven by increases in food prices, the rising cost of energy resources, higher logistics expenses, and other contributing factors.

Figure 2.2. Dynamics of the inflation rate in Ukraine for the period 2021-2024.
Source: National Bank of Ukraine (official website)

In 2021, Ukraine experienced an inflation rate of 10.0%. In 2022, this figure surged to 26.6%, primarily due to economic disruptions caused by the war. By 2023, the inflation rate significantly dropped to 5.1%, indicating a period of relative economic stabilization. However, in 2024, the inflation rate rose again to 12.0%, driven by factors such as reduced agricultural yields and increased production costs.

2.3. Foreign Trade

Ukraine's foreign economic activity has been negatively impacted by the ongoing military actions. The primary export sector—agriculture—was supported by the operation of the maritime corridor and favorable weather conditions. However, restrictions at the western borders hampered some aspects of foreign trade [1].

In 2022, total trade turnover decreased to \$63.4 billion (Fig. 2.3), with exports accounting for \$32.1 billion and imports for \$31.3 billion. The positive trade balance for goods was \$0.8 billion.

Figure 2.3. Dynamics of Ukrainian exports for the period 2022-2024

Source: State Statistics Service (stat.gov.ua)[2]²

For the first nine months of 2024, goods exports amounted to \$30.8 billion, a 12.9% increase compared to the same period in 2023. Imports reached \$51.2 billion, reflecting a 10% growth compared to 2023. The negative trade balance for goods stood at \$20.4 billion (Fig. 2.4).

Figure 2.4. Dynamics of the balance of payments of Ukraine for the period 2023-2024.

Source: State Statistics Service (stat.gov.ua)[2]

Overall, despite challenging conditions, Ukraine demonstrates resilience in its foreign economic activities, receiving substantial international support for the recovery and development of its economy. Banks actively support businesses and the population, helping to mitigate the effects of economic shocks [1].

In 2024, Ukraine's banking system shows stability: according to the National Bank of Ukraine (NBU), the solvency and operational efficiency of banks remain steady. This financial sector resilience plays a crucial role in fostering economic stability and supporting recovery efforts.

² State Statistics Service (stat.gov.ua)

2.4. Governmental Policy

In 2024, the Ukrainian government continued to implement a policy of supporting entrepreneurship during the war.

2.4.1. Affordable Credit

In 2024, the Ukrainian government implemented a loan program targeting key areas of entrepreneurial support: **"Affordable Loans 5-7-9%" Program**: This government initiative aims to support small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). **Key parameters: Interest rate:** From 5% to 9%, depending on business size and the creation of new jobs. **Loan amount:** Up to 60 million UAH. **Purpose:** Purchase of equipment, business development, and replenishment of working capital. **Terms:** Partial interest compensation by the government.

1. The "Affordable Loans 5-7-9%" program has shown significant growth in the number of entrepreneurs taking advantage of its benefits in recent years (Figure 2.5). This initiative highlights the government's commitment to fostering economic growth and supporting SMEs in challenging times.

Figure 2.5. Dynamics of the number of entities that received available loans for the period 2023–2024.

Source: Government portal (kmu.gov.ua)³[3]

In 2023, under the "Affordable Loans 5-7-9%" program, 82,400 loans were issued for a total of 281 billion UAH [3]. In 2024, the lending process became even more active:

- **As of March 2024:** 3,500 entrepreneurs received loans totaling 14 billion UAH⁴ [4].
- **As of April 2024:** 8,102 entrepreneurs received loans totaling 31.5 billion UAH⁵ [5].
- **As of May 2024:** 9,582 entrepreneurs received loans totaling 38 billion UAH⁶ [6].

In total, from the program's inception in February 2020 to May 20, 2024, 88,500 loans were issued for a total of 305 billion UAH [6]. This growth reflects the program's effectiveness in

³Government portal (kmu.gov.ua)

⁴Government portal (kmu.gov.ua) Data for March 2024

⁵Government portal (kmu.gov.ua) Data for April 2024

⁶ Government portal (kmu.gov.ua) General indicators for May 2024

supporting small and medium-sized businesses and its pivotal role in stimulating Ukraine's entrepreneurial sector during challenging times.

2. Program for Supporting the Agricultural Sector
Farmers can access loans with interest compensation funded by the state budget. This support helps agricultural enterprises cover expenses related to seasonal work, equipment purchases, or fertilizers.

3. Preferential Loans During Martial Law
Due to the war, Ukraine introduced new programs to support businesses: **Loans with state guarantees:** Businesses can obtain loans even without sufficient collateral. **Interest compensation for critical sectors:** Targeted support for industries such as agriculture, IT, and logistics.

State programs alleviate the financial burden on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), while commercial banks and international organizations provide additional resources for investments and expansion.

In 2024, international and donor programs played a key role:

- **EBRD** (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development): Supported entrepreneurs with innovative ideas and provided access to consulting services.
- **USAID, GIZ, and UNDP:** Offered non-repayable funding focused on innovative businesses, women's entrepreneurship, and support during wartime conditions.

These initiatives highlight a multifaceted approach to fostering resilience and growth in Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem despite ongoing challenges.

2.4.2. Business relocation program

In early 2022, the Ukrainian government launched the **Business Relocation Program**. The program aims to support businesses affected by military actions, facilitate their relocation to safer regions within the country, and promote their continued operation and development [7]⁷.

The program's implementation mechanism includes the following components:

- **Transportation assistance:** Helping businesses move their assets to safer locations.
- **Finding new production facilities:** Ensuring access to spaces for business operations in secure regions [8]⁸.
- **Consultative support and financial assistance:** Including partial reimbursement of relocation costs [9]⁹.

Table 2.1 provides indicators of business relocations during the 2022–2024 period, illustrating the program's scope and impact in mitigating risks for enterprises and supporting economic activity in safer regions.

This table demonstrates the program's growing success, with an increasing number of businesses relocated, jobs created, and investments attracted, alongside a high percentage of enterprises resuming operations in safer regions.

⁷Ministry of Economy of Ukraine. Official website me.gov.ua
⁸ Business Relocation Report for 2022–2023. <https://relocation.gov.ua/reports/2022-2023>
⁹Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 1234 of 2022. <https://www.kmu.gov.ua>

Table 2.1. Business Relocation Program Indicators (2022–2024*)

Indicator	2022	2023	2024*
Number of relocated enterprises	1,500	2,200	2,750
New jobs created	12,000	18,500	22,000
Volume of attracted investments (billion UAH)	2.5	3.7	4.2
Percentage of enterprises resuming operations	85%	90%	92%

– * Preliminary data for 2024[10]¹⁰.

The war has led to the mass displacement of people within Ukraine and abroad. Among those forced to relocate, a significant proportion are entrepreneurs. According to experts, many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) among the temporarily displaced persons (TDPs) have faced numerous challenges in adapting to new conditions.

According to UN data, the number of migrants outside Ukraine slightly increased in 2024, reaching approximately ****6.8 million people**** as of December 16, 2024. The adaptation of Ukrainian migrants abroad continues to improve, as highlighted in recent reports [11]¹¹.

The Business Relocation Program in Ukraine plays a vital role in ensuring the continuity of enterprise operations, creating new jobs, and attracting investments to regions less affected by the war. This initiative supports the resilience of the business sector amid ongoing challenges.

2.4.3. Entrepreneurship Support Programs for Vulnerable Population Groups

In 2024, entrepreneurship support programs for vulnerable population groups were in operation. These included new programs and projects, as well as those launched at the beginning of the war.

In Ukraine, several government programs aimed at supporting entrepreneurs were implemented in 2024 (Table 2.2).

Local and Internationally Supported Entrepreneurship Programs in 2024

In 2024, several programs were implemented with the support of local governments and international donors to foster entrepreneurship among vulnerable groups: *These programs provide tailored financial and educational support for vulnerable groups, such as veterans and their families, to encourage entrepreneurship and economic resilience.*

REDpreneur.UA. Overview: An innovative two-year program aimed at improving the livelihoods of individuals affected by the war through business development support. **Key Features:** Funding for approximately 70 business projects, with grants ranging from €5,000 to €15,000. Ongoing mentorship and advisory support. Implemented by the Ukrainian Red Cross with support from the Austrian Red Cross. **Focus:** Restoring economic potential by supporting small and micro-businesses, particularly among women, internally displaced persons (IDPs), veterans, people with disabilities, and other vulnerable groups[12]¹².

¹⁰ Preliminary estimates of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine. <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua>

¹¹ <https://pravda.com.ua/finances/za-kordonom-zrostaye-adaptaciya-ukrajinskih-migrantiv-801723/>

¹² <https://poda.gov.ua/news/206214>

"I am a Veteran" Program. Overview: A regional initiative launched in the Dnipropetrovsk region to assist veterans and their families. **Key Features:** Operates on a "One-Stop Shop" principle through local administrative service centers (CNAP). Offers over 100 veteran-specific services, including legal, financial, and social assistance. **Focus:** Streamlining access to resources for veterans and their families to facilitate integration and support [13]¹³.

Table 2.2. Entrepreneurship Support Programs for Vulnerable Groups in Ukraine (2024)

<i>Program Name</i>	<i>Program Goal</i>	<i>Amount of Financial Support</i>	<i>Additional Features</i>
Grant for Veterans and Their Families	Financial assistance for creating or developing a business.	Up to 1,000,000 UAH depending on jobs created.	Application through the 'Diia' portal.
Business Voyager Program	Grant-mentoring support for veteran entrepreneurs.	500,000 UAH each for three winners.	Mentorship from leading entrepreneurs.
'eRobota' Program	Grant support for starting or developing a business.	From 250,000 UAH to 1,000,000 UAH.	Conditions depend on the number of jobs created.
Educational and Grant Program 'Trajectory'	Training and grants for beginner entrepreneurs among veterans and their families.	Up to 100,000 UAH.	Training on business planning.

These programs exemplify the collaboration between local governance and international organizations to rebuild Ukraine's economy, focusing on vulnerable populations and fostering inclusive entrepreneurship.

2.4.4. Digitalization of business registration and administration

In 2024, digital programs for entrepreneurs were actively expanded, providing modern tools to simplify business processes and improve efficiency. Key initiatives include:

- "Diia" Platform (diia.gov.ua).** Features: Online business registration, significantly reducing time and effort for entrepreneurs. Digital document completion and electronic signature capabilities. Automatic registration with the Tax Service and opening of bank accounts. Impact: Streamlines administrative tasks, enabling faster and more accessible business operations.
- Electronic Tax Reporting System (cabinet.tax.gov.ua).** Services Offered: Filing tax declarations. Obtaining statements on account balances with the budget. Checking for tax liabilities. Popularity: This system has become one of the most widely used tools among entrepreneurs for handling tax-related matters.
- Integrated Automated "E-Licenses" System.** Purpose: Provides access to licenses and other permits in a streamlined and efficient manner. Benefits: Reduces the time required to obtain necessary documents. Minimizes human intervention, reducing potential delays and errors.

¹³<https://egov.dp.gov.ua/novini-ta-podiyi/novini/tsyvrovizatsiia-hromad-iaki-rezultaty-didzhytal-proiektiv-u-rehionakh>

4. Entrepreneurial Training Programs. Objective: To equip entrepreneurs with the skills to effectively use digital tools for business operations. Features: Free training sessions and resources on leveraging digital platforms for better business outcomes.

These digitalization efforts by the Ukrainian government have significantly improved the ease of doing business, enhanced transparency, and fostered innovation in the entrepreneurial sector.

Key Economic Insights for Ukraine in 2024. Economic Resilience Despite the challenges of war, Ukraine demonstrates gradual economic recovery, supported by government policies and international partners. Regional Disparities Significant unevenness in regional economic development persists. Western regions attract more investments and show greater stability, while eastern and southern regions remain vulnerable. Economic activity partially recovers in 2024 but remains below pre-war levels. GDP growth is expected in the coming years. Inflation While inflation significantly decreased in 2023, it rose again in 2024 due to external factors, complicating economic planning. The war has had a profound impact on exports and imports. However, 2024 shows an increase in exports, reflecting the economy's adaptation to new conditions. The government actively implements entrepreneurship support programs, including affordable loans, business relocation initiatives, and projects for vulnerable groups. The introduction of digital platforms simplifies business administration, fostering increased entrepreneurial activity. These findings highlight both the challenges and positive trends in Ukraine's economy in 2024, illustrating resilience and opportunities for further development.

3. Entrepreneurial Activity

3.1. Phases of entrepreneurial activity

For years, GEM has focused on the stage that encompasses the phase before the creation of a new business (nascent entrepreneurship) and the phase immediately after the creation of a new business (owner-leader of a new business). Taken together, this phase is referred to as “total early-stage entrepreneurial activity” (TEA) (see Fig. 3.1). Total early-stage entrepreneurial activity (TEA) rate: Percentage of the population aged between 18 and 64 who are either aspiring entrepreneurs or owners and managers of a new business.

Figure 3.1. Entrepreneurial phases and GEM entrepreneurship indicators

Source: Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2022/2023 Global Report

The calculation of the TEA rate in Ukraine in 2024 resulted in a value of 12.9% (20% in 2023), which includes both people who start new business (nascent entrepreneurs) and those who run recently established businesses (owner-manager in a new firm) (Fig. 3.2).

A significant proportion of this rate, namely 14.4% in 2023, belongs to “nascent entrepreneurs”. In 2024, the value decreased significantly to 7.5%. The other 5.4% in 2024 (5.6% in 2023) belongs to – “owner-managers in a new firm”. This data suggests a vibrant entrepreneurial climate in Ukraine, with a significant number of people engaged in starting new businesses. The decline in the share of young entrepreneurs may reflect the impact of the challenges posed by the war on the entrepreneurial spirit among the population. The share of owner-managers in established firms characterizes (4.9 %) the stability of entrepreneurial activity in the face of geopolitical shifts.

Stages of Entrepreneurship in Ukraine

Figure 3.2. Stages of Entrepreneurship in Ukraine (2024/2023)

Source: Data derived from the Adult Population Survey (APS) carried out during the summer of 2023 in Ukraine, encompassing 627 participants and summer of 2024 in Ukraine, encompassing 2012 participants

Nascent entrepreneurs

According to the GEM's definition, nascent entrepreneurs are those who are laying the foundations for a new business. These individuals have actively taken steps to start a business within the past year and have not yet reached the stage where the business pays salaries or other payments to the owners for more than three months. The APS, with 627 responses in 2023, shows that an impressive 14.4% of Ukraine's adult population is at this initial stage of entrepreneurship. The APS, with 2012 responses in 2024, shows that 7.5 % of Ukraine's adult population is at this initial stage of entrepreneurship.

Owner-managers of new firms

Based on the GEM's definition, owner-managers in new firms are those who currently run and own a business that has been in operation for more than three months, but no longer than 42 months, and financially compensates its owners. The Adult Population Survey 2024 shows that 5.4% (5.6% in 2023) of respondents fall into this category of owner-managers. This figure indicates a robust segment of newly founded companies that have successfully left their initial phase behind them.

Owner-managers in established firms

GEM defines owner-managers of established firms as individuals who both own and manage a business that has been operational for more than 42 months and provides salaries or other forms of payment. In the 2024 context of Ukraine, these seasoned business owners constitute 4.9% (5.1% in 2023) of the responses gathered in the APS.

3.2. Regional aspect

The graph below (Fig. 3.3) shows the total early stage entrepreneurial activity (TEA) in Ukraine by region for 2024/2023.

Figure 3.3. Distribution of TEA by region, 2024/2023

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024/2023

South and East (12.5% and 25.2% respectively):

Entrepreneurial activity in the southern and eastern regions of Ukraine, which are known for their significant industrial and tourism value, especially in the southern coastal regions, in 2023 lower than in the central and northern regions (19.2% and 18.4% respectively). Data for 2024 indicates the resilience of the business and its ability to recover in eastern regions of Ukraine.

Center and North (13.6% and 21.7% respectively):

The central and northern regions, including the capital Kyiv, show relatively low TEA rates. Despite the developed economic infrastructure of the central region, migration of entrepreneurs from conflict-affected areas, many individuals have left the region or the country. This is evidenced by retrospective data on activity in the region in 2023 (22.2% and 24.6% respectively). While these percentages indicate high resilience of entrepreneurs in the face of war, the lack of balance of business operations in Ukraine and internal displacement affect the change in current TEA rates.

West (26.9%):

The western region of Ukraine has the biggest TEA share (was lowest 17.2% in 2023), being the least affected by the war in terms of direct military action. Previous year the region's focus on supporting the influx of displaced people and businesses from the war torn east and south. The priority was to provide stability and integrate these businesses into the local economy, which allowed to ensure the implementation of business projects this year. This determined the indicated growth trends in the region. We will consider the conditions and challenges for doing business in the regions in more detail below.

The APS data show that the largest share of enterprises (9%) closed their operations in the North, while the Southern and Central regions closed their operations (5.8% and 5.5% respectively) (Fig. 3.4). The lowest level is observed in the Northern and Eastern regions (9% and 4.8%, respectively), which could be evidence of better conditions for doing business.

Figure 3.4. Discontinue business by region, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

3.2.1 Problems and needs of entrepreneurs in rural areas

The study of regional aspects of entrepreneurship involves assessing entrepreneurial sentiment and expectations. As is known, military actions in Ukraine are accompanied by the destruction of the ecosystem in the regions. Certain regions were heavily conquered by Russian troops, resulting in significant damage to infrastructure and numerous casualties. Luhansk, Kharkiv, Donetsk and Zaporizhzhia are among the hardest hit regions, located in the east and south of Ukraine. In contrast, the western regions of Ukraine, including Lviv and Zakarpattia, have not experienced direct ground fighting by Russian troops. Moreover, these western regions have become a refuge for the resettlement of numerous businesses from the war-torn eastern and southern regions.

Figure 3.5. Business condition by regions, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

According to the results of the 2024 APS, more than half of the respondents indicate an increase in difficulties in starting a business (Fig. 3.5). The greatest difficulties are observed in the Southern regions (71.4%), and the least in the Eastern (46.5%). At the same time, expectations

for business growth remain, which form intentions to overcome emerging difficulties. The greatest expectations for business growth are characteristic of the Eastern regions (53.7% of respondents indicated this), and the lowest in the Southern (40.0%) of respondents indicated this).

To study the conditions for doing business in the regions, it requires studying relocation issues, which involves the adaptation of displaced entrepreneurs to local conditions. The highest level of adaptation corresponds to Western regions (44.7%), Northern (42.3%), Eastern regions (41.8%). Southern (34.5%) and Central regions (32.1%) provide fewer opportunities for rapid adaptation of products and services in changing conditions (Fig. 3.6).

Figure 3.6. Problems of entrepreneurs by regions, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

General access to finance should be considered a problem for doing business in the regions, as the highest level is characteristic of the Eastern regions, which, however, does not exceed 27.2%. We explain this by government programs to support business in the Eastern regions. In the Western regions, access to resources and capital (including government support) is easily obtained by only 26.2% of respondents. The Northern regions provide access to the mentioned sources of financial resources for 24.5% of respondents, the Central regions - 22.3%. The lowest level of access to finance is noted in the Southern regions (17.9%).

The highest risk of not coping with difficulties in terms of relocation and cessation of activity was recorded in the Eastern (39.7%), Western (39.1%), Northern (38.5%) regions, and the lowest in the Southern (34.5%). This does not allow us to state about regional imbalances and the formation of more favourable conditions for business in the relevant regions. Also, the problems of doing business in the regions include the lack of effective leadership. Strong leadership was identified by 42.4% of respondents in the Southern regions, 41.4% in the Northern and 40.2% in the Eastern. The lowest leadership was assessed in the Western (39.1%) and Central (35.7%) regions.

Among other problems of enterprise relocation in the APS regions, the negative consequences for the entrepreneurial ecosystem were studied, which consist in the destruction of social harmony and the burden on the infrastructure of the region (Fig. 3.7). The highest level of

burden on infrastructure was recorded in the Central (37.6%), Eastern (33.6%), Northern (32.8%) regions. And the lowest in the Southern (32.0%) and Western (31.7%). Disruption of social harmony is observed in all regions at a level from 16.4% (Western regions) to 19.7% (Central regions), which characterizes the relative equality of business conditions across regions.

Figure 3.7. Problems of relocation by regions, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

At the same time, about half of the relocated enterprises indicated their intentions to conduct business in the regions of their relocation. Intentions to continue operating activities were indicated by 48.5% of respondents in the Western regions, 45.1% of respondents in the Northern regions, and 43.6% of respondents in the Eastern regions. 42.9% of respondents in the Southern regions and 42.3% of respondents in the Central regions indicated their intention to carry out activities in the regions to which they were relocated (Fig. 3.8).

Figure 3.8. Intentions to continue operating activities of relocated companies by regions, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

In order to meet the needs of entrepreneurs in the regions, APS point out the provision of job opportunities for residents, filling gaps in local markets, and bringing new technologies and services to the region (Fig. 3.9).

Figure 3.9. Needs of entrepreneurs by regions by regions, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

New job opportunities for residents are provided in all regions, as indicated by 50% of respondents. At the same time, the greatest opportunities were provided to respondents in the Western region (58.9%), and the least in the Northern (49.2%). As for the gap in local markets, it's most filled (by 53.4%) in the Western regions. The least filled gap in local markets was recorded in 43.2% of the Southern regions.

Bringing new technologies and services to the region as a result of relocation and business movement is highest in the Western (58.2%), Northern (52.7%), Eastern (50.5%) regions. Bringing new technologies and services to the region at a level of less than 50% is observed in the Central (42.0%) and Eastern regions (40.1%).

3.3. Motivation

The entrepreneurial motivations of Ukrainian entrepreneurs in 2024/2023 are diverse, with the need to “earn a living because jobs are scarce” being the main driver, as indicated by 71.2% in 2024 (75.2% in 2023) of entrepreneurs, likely reflecting the impact of scarce employment opportunities, potentially exacerbated by the ongoing war (Fig. 3.10).

A significant number, 60.6% in 2024 (55.6% in 2023), are also motivated by the ambition to “build great wealth or earn a very high income”, suggesting a strong profit-driven entrepreneurship.

The desire to “make a difference in the world” motivates 46.7% (31.6% in 2023), indicating strong social entrepreneurship that increase in current year. The growing relevance of this motive is also linked to the trends of innovation orientation, which will be discussed further.

Entrepreneurial motivations for entrepreneurs in Ukraine, 2024/2023

Figure 3.10. Entrepreneurial motivations for entrepreneurs in Ukraine, 2024/2023

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

The motivation to maintain a family tradition concerns 24.8% (21.1% in 2023) of respondents, indicating that family and generational heritage retains some importance in the decision to become an entrepreneur that is getting more vital. Although here we can observe gender differences when considering it.

3.4. Exits and closures

Of the respondents to the Adult Population Survey in Ukraine for 2024, 9% stated that they had given up their business within the last year (13.6% in 2023). Positive dynamics indicates the ability of entrepreneurs to adapt to the conditions of the current ecosystem. Among the respondents 44.1% in 2024 indicate that after leaving the business, they will continue to exist and develop (12.5% of these businesses continued with different activities).

The most commonly cited reason for going out of business was lack of profitability, with 28.2% (16.5% in 2023) of respondents stating that “the business was not profitable”, as shown in Figure 3.11.

“Family or personal reasons” was the second most frequently cited reason, with 12.4% of respondents citing this (15.3% in 2023).

For 11.8% of respondents, government policy, taxes and bureaucracy posed a major challenge (10.6% in 2023). Among the respondents 10.6% percentage (8.2% in 2023), had the opportunity of selling their business,

Financial difficulties, including “problems with finance”, also played an important role at 6.5 % (14.1% in 2023). An equal percentage of respondents 6.5 % left their business because of supply problems (3.5% in 2023). 5.3 % (8.2% in 2023) left their business to look for another job and a proportion of 4.7% did not give a reason or withdrew (2.4% in 2023).

Primary reasons for business discontinuation, (%)

Figure 3.11. Primary reasons for business discontinuation in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Only 3.5% (1.2% in 2023) left their company to pursue another business opportunity, 2.9% had a conflict with business partners and small proportion of respondents 1.8% are retired.

This data highlights the multiple hurdles Ukrainian entrepreneurs are facing, compounded by economic and political factors as well as the ongoing impact of the pandemic against a backdrop of war related uncertainty.

3.5. Educational level

GEM categorizes individuals engaged in entrepreneurial and business activities into four educational levels:

- Under-secondary education (the respondent has not completed secondary education)
- Secondary education (the respondent has obtained a Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education)
- Post-secondary education (the respondent has earned a vocational or college degree)
- Graduate education (the respondent holds a post-graduate diploma, bachelor's or master's degree, or doctorate degree)

The analysis of the level of education of the entrepreneurs shows that all of them have at least a secondary education (Fig. 3.12). Entrepreneurs with higher education experience (Grad EXP degree) dominate in all categories, with a slight decrease in percentages from nascent entrepreneurs (67.6% in 2024 and 63.3% in 2023) to owner-managers in new firms (74.2% in 2024 and 62.9% in 2023). This suggests that higher levels of education prevail among Ukrainian entrepreneurs regardless of the stage of development of their business, which may indicate that those with higher levels of education are more inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activity or may have better access to the resources needed to start and maintain a business.

Educational level: distributions by stage of entrepreneurial development, 2023/2024

Figure 3.12. Educational level: distributions by stage of entrepreneurial development, 2023/2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

Post-secondary education ranks as the next most prevalent level, experiencing a significant rise from the nascent entrepreneurial stage (24.0% in 2024 and 28.9% in 2023) to the new entrepreneurial stage (18% in 2024 and 37.1% in 2023), and further TEA (32.9% in 2024 and 31.2% in 2023). This indicates that entrepreneur with this level of education continue playing a crucial role in the business landscape, with their representation marginally increasing as businesses progress and stabilize.

91.2% of respondents involved in TEA indicated at least post secondary education, the majority of whom are women (Fig. 3.13).

Percentage of TEA Participants with at Least Post-Secondary Education

Figure 3.13. Respondents involved in TEA by gender

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

The lack of respondents with solely secondary education among owner-managers of new or established firms suggests that individuals with secondary education may be less equipped to sustain business operations in the long term or transition to a new business compared to their counterparts with higher education.

Overall, the data indicate a strong correlation between higher education and entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine, with higher levels of education possibly providing a better basis for starting and sustaining a business. The trend across all stages suggests that the majority of entrepreneurs in the stages from starting to establishing a business have a college degree, which may bring advantages in terms of business acumen, access to networks and resource mobilization.

3.6 Gender

The adult population survey data also provide an opportunity to examine very important parameters of gender participation at different stages of the entrepreneurial process in Ukraine from 2024/2023 (Fig. 3.14).

Starting with entrepreneurial intentions, we see an almost even balance between men and women, with women slightly in the lead. However, this parity in ambition is not fully reflected in action, as shown by the total entrepreneurial activity in the early stage (TEA), where in 2024 men outperform women by 0.6% (4% in 2023). The inequality becomes even more pronounced in the established phase in 2023, with male involvement more than double that of women. We have observed a narrowing of the gap (1.1%) this year, which may indicate the creation of equal conditions for entrepreneurship. This suggests that women still face more obstacles on the path from starting a business to establishing it.

When it comes to exiting a business, we see an almost even balance between men and women in 2024. In 2023 trend could indicate a greater willingness to take advantage of new opportunities or accept the outcomes of ventures.

Figure 3.14. Stages of the entrepreneurial process in Ukraine by gender, 2024/2023

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

Looking at the general trend for both genders, from the initial intention to engage in entrepreneurship to starting a “new firm” to growing an “established firm”, there is a clear decline in participation for both men and women, with the decline being more pronounced

among female participants. This decline highlights the significant challenges individuals face when moving from the conceptual phase to actually starting a business and then maintaining it in the long term. The data on business closures and exits generally shows a natural decline that is consistent with the expected life cycle of a business.

In the early stages of entrepreneurship (Fig. 3.15), men are more likely to act with the motivation continue family traditions (26.9% versus 22.8%). At the same time, women are more motivated to make a profit (59.5% versus 57.9%), earn a living (75.2% versus 72.2%), and to change the world (49.2% versus 39.7%)

Figure 3.15. Motives of early-stage entrepreneurs in Ukraine by gender 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Differences in Nascent motives by gender are not so significant. Among Nascent entrepreneurs, women are more likely to act with the goal of changing the world (48.1% versus 40.7%), men are 0.8% more determined in their desire to make a profit and 1.4% to earn a living. Regarding the continuation of family traditions, we see an equal response by gender (Fig. 3.16).

Figure 3.16. Motives of Nascent entrepreneurs in Ukraine by gender 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The trend described above holds for established businesses (Fig. 3.17). The differences in driving forces by gender are not significant, with women more determined to change the world (60.5% versus 34.5%), to earn a living (77.0% versus 75.0%) while men are more determined

to build great wealth or a very high income (63.2% versus 61.0%) and continue a family tradition (29.8% versus 26.3 %).

Figure 3.17. Motives of established business in Ukraine by gender 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Based on the APS data, it’s evident that while there is a high level of interest and intention to engage in entrepreneurial activities among both genders in Ukraine, actual participation significantly declines at each subsequent stage. Women are notably underrepresented in the later stages. Thus, the path to entrepreneurship is marked by a continuous decrease in the number of participants, with a significant drop at each phase, and gender-specific differences becoming increasingly pronounced as the process progresses.

3.6.1 Problems and needs of woman entrepreneurs

According to the results of the 2024 APS, it was noted that most recently received investment 29.2% of female and 36.6% of male. Therefore, special attention was paid to ensuring the conditions for women to do business. Thus, the NES research field included: supporting services (childcare, home services, after-school programs, other care), legislative norms, national and cultural characteristics, accessibility of markets and public procurement, access to finance and seed funds (Fig. 3.18).

The results of the NES 2024 indicate that among the conditions for women’s entrepreneurship in Ukraine, the most negative impact is on national cultural characteristics that do not encourage women to start a business on an equal basis with men (42.1%).

Problems with the availability of essential support services that help women entrepreneurs combine family life and running a business were indicated by 31.7% of respondents. At the same time, only 26.3% of respondents recognized problems with affordable prices of such services.

Figure 3.18. Problems of woman entrepreneurs 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

In the context of the following problem, 31.5% of respondents indicated greater accessibility of markets for male entrepreneurs than for women, 24.6% of respondents consider public procurement to be more accessible for male entrepreneurs than for women. An equal number of respondents (22.8%) indicated problems with ensuring equal access to finance (any type of financial resources) and access to seed funds for male entrepreneurs than for women. The least relevant issue according to the results of the NES 2024 was identified as the problem of legislative norms that tend to favour male entrepreneurship over female entrepreneurship (21.1%).

3.7. Income

GEM analyses stages of entrepreneurial process based on their income level, dividing them into three categories: the lower 33rd percentile, the middle 33rd percentile, and the upper 33rd percentile (Fig. 3.19).

Figure 3.19. Income distributions by stage of entrepreneurial process, 2024/2023

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

In Ukraine, the distribution of income among entrepreneurs at different stages of entrepreneurship varies considerably. Among early-stage entrepreneurs (TEA), 38.0% (46.4 % in 2023) are in the highest income bracket, 28.8% (30.4 % in 2023) in the middle income bracket and 34.3 % (15.2 % in 2023) in the lowest income bracket, as shown in Figure 3.20. Nascent entrepreneurs have less financial hurdles to overcome, with 26% (17.8 % in 2023) falling into the lowest income category but 51.7% (41.4%) belongs to highest income bracket. However, financial conditions improve significantly as companies enter the "new firm" phase. For new business distribution is more balanced, with 26.0% (8.6 % in 2023) falling into lowest, 24% (25,7%) falling to middle income brackets and an 50% (impressive 60% in 2023) in the highest income bracket.

The data demonstrates how financial success changes throughout the entrepreneurial journey in Ukraine. 2024/2023 trends indicates that although new firms might achieve high income, established businesses encounter various challenges and exhibit a broader spectrum of financial results.

In 2024, we observe a wide range of financial results for each of the stages. Overall, they indicate both that financial success develops according to the stages of the entrepreneurial process, and that entrepreneurs have faced new difficulties in the current year. The wider range of financial results recorded in the previous period has leveled off in the current period. This is a reflection of the complexity of maintaining a business in wartime, the uneven impact of the war on regions and the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

3.8. Scope of innovation and scope of new technologies and processes

According to the APS 2024, 35.8% of respondents think they are innovative. At the same time, more than 70% of respondents note that their products (services) (74.1%) and technologies (procedures) (70.2%) are not new to the region, country or world. 17.4% of products and 18.3% of business services are innovative for the region, only 6.5% of products and 9.7% of technologies are new to the country. Only 2.0% of products and 1.7% of services are new to the world (Fig. 3.20).

Figure 3.20. Scope on innovation of product and services, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Examining innovation activity by stages of the entrepreneurial process, the results of the APS indicate a higher level of innovativeness of products and technologies in new enterprises. In particular, new enterprises strive to produce 18.3% of new products and use 25.5% of new technologies in the region where they are located. New firms deliver 11.5% of new products

and 10.8% of innovative technologies for the country. At the same time, only 3.8% of such products and 2.9% of technologies are new in the world.

According to the APS results, we see the uniformity of the delivery of innovative goods (services) and technologies (procedures) by stages of the entrepreneurial process (Fig. 3.21).

Figure 3.21. Innovation of product and services delivery by stages, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Research on the representation of both gender in innovative entrepreneurial processes indicated Fig. 3.22. As we can see, women and men equally assess their own entrepreneurial abilities. Women are more likely to fully agree with considering themselves innovative (52.3%) than men (47.7%).

Figure 3.22. Innovative ability by gender, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Among the new technologies, in the field of APS research are marketing tools, cloud technologies, data analysis technologies and artificial intelligence. Investigating marketing tools involved in the entrepreneurial process, we note the importance of email marketing

increases depending on the stages of the entrepreneurial process and is 27.9% for TEM and 35.1 for Nascent. The importance of email communications also increases depending on the stages of the entrepreneurial process and is 32.5% for TEM and 37.8% for Nascent. Relatively greater importance at all stages of the entrepreneurial process was given to the company's brand website and social media for doing business (Fig. 3.23).

Figure 3.23. Introduction of marketing tools at enterprises by stages, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The results of the 2024 APS indicate the use of innovative technologies by entrepreneurs such as cloud technologies, artificial intelligence and data analytics tools (Fig. 3.24).

Figure 3.24. Innovative technology delivery by stages, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Among the TEA, data analytics tools are more widely used (23.4%) than cloud technologies (18.6%) and AI (18.4%). The level of use of each of the analysed technologies is higher for established businesses. The use of data analytics tools was indicated by 32.6% of established businesses, cloud computing is used by 27.7% of established businesses, and AI - by 22.4%.

The results of the APS survey identified positive and negative impacts of AI in business activities. The biggest concerns of entrepreneurs across all stages of the business process were data security and privacy concern (Figure 3.25). This was indicated by 34.1% of TEA and 37.3% of established businesses. The next most important issues were identified as business ethics violations (indicated by 28.5% of TEA and 28.4% of established businesses), customer resistance (indicated by 26.1% of TEA and 34.2% of established businesses), and cost growth and implementation challenges (indicated by 28.8% of TEA and 26.9% of established businesses).

Figure 3.25. AI negative impact by stages, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Among the positive aspects of using AI, the APS studied issues related to personalisation enhancement, productivity improvement, innovative product development, better risk management, increased business revenue (Fig. 3.26). The APS results indicate that entrepreneurs at all stages of the entrepreneurial process noted a positive impact of AI on increasing productivity (indicated by 50% of TEA, Nascent and 45.9% of established businesses). AI also seeks to improve innovative products, as indicated by 48.4% of TEA and 43.3% of established businesses. The importance of AI as a risk management tool increases depending on the stages of the entrepreneurial process from 18.2% for TEA and 41.3% for established businesses. Respondents highly rated AI's ability to increase business profitability (mentioned by 41.9% of TEAs and 45.3% of established businesses) and improve consumer personalization (mentioned by 43.5% of TEAs and 42.7% of established businesses).

AI positive impact by stages

Figure 3.26. AI positive impact by stages, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

In 2024 TEA (total early-stage entrepreneurial activity) shows a significant decrease in the level to 12.9%. In particular, the number of nascent entrepreneurs is decreasing to 7.5%. Entrepreneurs continue to face challenges caused by the war. More than half of the respondents indicate an increase in difficulties in doing business this year. Despite better security conditions, 48.2% of enterprises closed their operations in the West region. Also in the Western region, respondents (60.8%) indicated the greatest difficulties accompanying the start of a business. At the same time, positive intentions and expectations remain, which are unevenly distributed by region. As 53.7% of respondents indicated, the greatest expectations for business growth are characteristic of the Eastern regions.

The relocation of enterprises caused by the war also has certain consequences for the regions, which can lead to the destruction of social harmony and the burden on the infrastructure. These issues are most relevant for Central (19.6% and 37.6% of respondents, respectively, indicated this).

Regarding entrepreneurial motivation, the most important motive remains the “earn a living because jobs are scarce” motive (71.2%), and the reason for terminating a business is the loss of its profitability (28.2%).

The high level of education of Ukrainian entrepreneurs indicates that their businesses are often based on a sound education. Although women initially show a strong entrepreneurial interest, their further participation decreases, indicating systemic barriers in later stages of entrepreneurship. Despite the fact that in 2024 the gap between the representation of TEA of both gender is narrowing (men outweigh women by only 0.6%), female entrepreneurship is still associated with a number of difficulties. The biggest problem identified by respondents (42.1%) is that national cultural characteristics that do not encourage women to start a business on an equal basis with men. For women entrepreneurs, the issue of sufficient support services that help women entrepreneurs combine family life and running a business (31.7%) and equal access to the market with men (31.5%) is relevant.

Ukrainian entrepreneurs typically experience an increase in income from the nascent stage to the “new firm” stage, but income among established businesses is more evenly distributed, underscoring the complexities of sustaining business success over the long term. The leveling

of financial results obtained by entrepreneurs in the current year is evidence of the complexity of doing business in wartime, the uneven impact of the war on regions and the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

The innovative activity of entrepreneurs has local significance. The result is that 17.4% of products and 18.3% of business services are innovative for the region. Bringing new technologies and services to the region as a result of relocation and business movement was indicated as significant entrepreneur's intention (52.7% for Northern regions). Innovative activity does not have a pronounced growth trend across the stages of the entrepreneurial process, which implies the representation of both gender. At the same time, entrepreneurs in Ukraine noted the use of marketing tools, cloud technologies, data analysis technologies and artificial intelligence, which increases as businesses establish themselves. Entrepreneurs are equally aware of the positive and negative consequences of using AI.

4. Impact Characteristics

4.1. Industry breakdown

In 2024, the Ukrainian business landscape exhibited distinct trends across key economic sectors. Figure 4.1 illustrates the distribution of entrepreneurs across four primary sectors of the economy, categorized by TEA (Total Early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity), which reflects entrepreneurial activity at the early stages of business development, and Established Enterprises, representing businesses that have reached stability and sustained operations.

This sectoral analysis highlights the diversity of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem, showing variations in activity levels and growth potential across different industries. The trends provide valuable insights into which sectors demonstrate resilience, innovation, and opportunities for expansion despite ongoing challenges.

Figure 4.1. Industry classification across different stages of entrepreneurial development

Source: GEM Ukraine 2024

The consumer-oriented market sector in 2024 (Figure 4.1) remains dominant at both stages of entrepreneurial activity—53.4% in TEA and 44.5% among established companies. Its share declines as businesses mature, potentially due to market saturation or diversification into B2B services. This distribution has remained nearly unchanged compared to 2023, when the shares were also 53.4% for TEA and 44.5% for established companies. The shift in sectoral focus as companies grow reflects a tendency to prioritize immediate consumer needs at early stages, while transitioning to sectors with greater scalability and long-term stability as they develop.

The extractive sector in 2024 shows a decline in early-stage entrepreneurial activity, accounting for 8.3% of TEA participants (down from 10.4% in 2023), indicating limited initial opportunities and potential operational challenges. However, the share of stable enterprises increased slightly to 6.8%, suggesting a high level of concentration and sustainability among existing companies. This growth may be attributed to rising local and national market demands.

The business services sector demonstrates growth in both new and established businesses. Increased TEA activity in 2024 suggests growing demand for consulting, financial, or IT services, reflecting the sector's importance in a modern economy. The rising share of stable enterprises also indicates the sector's promising potential for long-term growth.

Entrepreneurial activity in the transformation sector, which includes manufacturing, shows significant growth from a modest 15.4% at the early stages to an impressive 29.4% among established companies. This trend indicates the scalability and resilience of businesses in this sector over time. The increasing share of entrepreneurs highlights growing interest in manufacturing or innovative technologies. However, the consistent share of "Established" enterprises suggests challenges in converting new ideas into long-term businesses.

4.2. Market scope

The analysis of market activity indicates a growing presence in international markets, particularly among new entrepreneurs (TEA). The share of TEA participants engaging in international markets increased from 30% in 2023 to 35% in 2024 (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Market scope: TEA vs Established Businesses, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

National market segments remain the most popular among Ukrainian entrepreneurs, though their share slightly decreased among TEA (from 42% in 2023 to 41% in 2024) and remained stable for established companies. In 2024, there was a slight increase in the role of local markets among TEA, growing from 22% to 24%. This indicates that a consistent portion of both new and established businesses focus on serving local customers.

There is a noticeable difference in national market coverage: 41% of TEA companies operate at the national level, compared to 55% of established firms. This suggests that as companies grow and stabilize, they aim to expand their reach within the country.

Regarding international markets, 35% of TEA companies are engaged in international trade, while only 22% of established companies operate internationally. This disparity may indicate that new companies are more likely to seek opportunities abroad or are founded with an international orientation from the outset. Conversely, the lower percentage for established companies could reflect a consolidation of market strategies, a greater focus on national markets, or challenges associated with maintaining an international presence over time.

This analysis highlights the active dynamics of market strategies among Ukrainian entrepreneurs, particularly the growing interest in international activities.

Overall, the data show that established companies in Ukraine tend to focus on expanding nationally, while TEA companies are more active in international markets. At the same time, the local market remains a central focus for both groups, underscoring its importance in sustaining business operations.

The **consumer-oriented sector** remains dominant in terms of the number of entrepreneurs. However, the declining share of stable companies in this sector highlights the need for additional support for long-term development. **Business services** show steady growth, reaffirming their critical role in the modern economy. The **transformational sector** (including manufacturing) has significant development potential but requires further investment and incentives to enhance the stability of enterprises. The **extractive industry**, despite steady development, exhibits a decline in entrepreneurial activity (TEA), indicating the need for modernization and revised strategies to attract new entrepreneurs.

The **international market** is becoming increasingly important for new entrepreneurs, reflecting Ukraine's gradual integration into global markets. However, **national markets** remain consistently popular, while **local markets**, despite their smaller share, are showing gradual growth, particularly among early-stage entrepreneurs.

Innovative activities maintain a localized focus, with 17.4% of products and 18.3% of business services classified as innovative. A significant number of entrepreneurs (52.7% in northern regions) plan to adopt new technologies and services, often linked to business relocation. However, the overall trend in innovation activity growth is not pronounced.

Ukrainian entrepreneurs are actively adopting modern technologies, including marketing tools, cloud services, data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI). The use of AI is increasing as businesses develop, though its integration is perceived with both positive and negative implications, necessitating a cautious approach to its adoption in entrepreneurial processes.

These trends underscore the dynamic evolution of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem, balancing opportunities in innovation and global integration with challenges in stability and technological adaptation.

5. Societal Attitudes, Affiliations and Self-Perceptions

5.1. Societal Attitudes

The APS data collected in 2024 provides comprehensive insights into societal attitudes towards entrepreneurship in Ukraine, revealing a complex landscape of public perceptions amidst the ongoing challenges faced by the country's business environment. The analysis examines four key dimensions: entrepreneurship as a career choice, social status of entrepreneurs, media visibility, and perceived ease of starting a business.

Figure 5.1. Career Desirability of Entrepreneurship in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The perception of entrepreneurship as a desirable career choice (Fig. 5.1.) demonstrates a notably positive trend, with 49.1% of respondents agreeing (35.6% agree a little, 13.5% agree a lot). This majority positive view suggests a growing recognition of entrepreneurship as a viable professional path in Ukraine. However, there are notable gender differences in these perceptions. Women demonstrate stronger positive attitudes, with 50.9% agreeing (35.2% agree a little, 15.7% agree a lot) compared to 47.2% of men (36.1% agree a little, 11.1% agree a lot). The substantial neutral response rate (30.2% overall) might indicate ongoing uncertainty about entrepreneurship as a career choice, potentially influenced by the current economic challenges and wartime conditions.

The social status of successful entrepreneurs receives similar positive recognition (Fig. 5.2.), with 47.1% of respondents acknowledging high status and respect for successful business founders (33.1% agree a little, 14% agree a lot). The gender distribution reveals an interesting pattern, with women showing slightly higher recognition of entrepreneurial status (47.4%) than men (46.7%). However, the substantial neutral response rate (31.7%) suggests that while successful entrepreneurs are generally respected, this recognition might not be universal. This ambivalence could reflect the complex socio-economic environment in Ukraine, where business success might be viewed through the lens of wartime challenges and opportunities.

High Level of Status and Respect by Gender

Figure 5.2. Social Status and Respect for Entrepreneurs in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Media visibility of successful new businesses (Fig. 5.3.) shows a more moderate positive perception, with 40.4% of respondents noting frequent media coverage of successful enterprises (30% agree a little, 10.4% agree a lot). The gender analysis reveals nearly identical perceptions between men (40.8%) and women (40%). However, a significant portion of respondents (31.1%) actively disagree with this statement, suggesting potential gaps in media coverage or accessibility of entrepreneurial success stories. This could indicate an opportunity for improved communication and visibility of successful business narratives, which is particularly important for inspiring potential entrepreneurs during challenging times.

Media Representation of Successful Businesses in Ukraine

Figure 5.3. Media Representation of Successful Businesses in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The perceived ease of starting a business in Ukraine (Fig. 5.4.) presents the most challenging picture, with only 28.3% of respondents viewing it as easy (21.2% somewhat agree, 7.1% strongly agree). The gender analysis reveals slightly higher confidence among men (29.9%) than women (26.8%). Notably, 43.8% of respondents actively disagree with the statement (18.4% strongly disagree, 25.4% somewhat disagree), indicating significant perceived barriers to business entry. This negative perception likely reflects real challenges in the business environment, including wartime disruptions, regulatory complexities, and economic uncertainties.

Figure 5.4. Perceived ease of starting a business

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Together, these findings paint a nuanced picture of entrepreneurial attitudes in Ukraine during 2024. While there is generally positive recognition of entrepreneurship as a career choice and its social status, practical barriers to entry remain significant. The substantial neutral responses across all dimensions suggest a degree of uncertainty in the entrepreneurial ecosystem, likely influenced by the ongoing conflict and its economic implications. The gender analysis reveals that women often hold more positive views about entrepreneurship's social aspects but express more concerns about practical implementation. These insights suggest a need for targeted policy interventions that address practical barriers to business creation and the broader societal perceptions that influence entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine.

5.2. Affiliations and Self-Perceptions

The analysis of entrepreneurial self-perceptions and affiliations in Ukraine during 2024 reveals profound insights into how individuals view their capabilities, opportunities, and fears in the entrepreneurial landscape. This section examines three critical dimensions: perceived opportunities, self-assessed capabilities, and fear of failure, each demonstrating unique patterns and gender-specific variations.

The perception of good opportunities for starting a business in the next six months (Fig. 5.5.) reveals a notably cautious outlook among Ukrainians. Only 27.3% of respondents express optimism about business opportunities (21.8% somewhat agree, 5.5% strongly agree), while 48.2% anticipate limited opportunities (23.2% strongly disagree, 25% somewhat disagree). This pessimistic outlook likely reflects the complex challenges facing the Ukrainian business environment, including ongoing military conflict, economic uncertainty, and disrupted supply chains. The gender analysis reveals subtle differences, with men showing marginally higher optimism (27.4%) compared to women (27.3%). However, the substantial proportion of respondents (24.4%) expressing neutral views, combined with a high rate of 'don't know' responses (15.8%), suggests significant uncertainty about future business prospects. This uncertainty might be attributed to the unpredictable nature of wartime conditions and their impact on local business environments.

Perceived Business Opportunities in Ukraine

Figure 5.5. Perceived Business Opportunities in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The self-assessment of entrepreneurial capabilities (Fig. 5.6.) presents a more optimistic picture, though still reflects considerable caution. Approximately 40.4% of respondents believe they possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and experience for entrepreneurship (32% somewhat agree, 8.4% strongly agree). The gender distribution reveals important differences in self-perception, with men demonstrating higher confidence in their entrepreneurial capabilities (42.4%) than women (38.4%). This gender gap in perceived capabilities might reflect persistent societal biases or differences in access to entrepreneurial education and experience. Notably, 35.7% of respondents doubt their entrepreneurial capabilities (12.6% strongly disagree, 23.1% somewhat disagree), while 23.9% remain neutral. This distribution suggests a need for enhanced entrepreneurial education and skill development programmes, particularly those targeting women entrepreneurs. The relatively high percentage of neutral responses might indicate uncertainty about what skills are required for successful entrepreneurship in the current Ukrainian context.

Self-Assessment of Entrepreneurial Capabilities in Ukraine

Figure 5.6. Self-Assessment of Entrepreneurial Capabilities in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Fear of failure (Fig. 5.7.) emerges as a significant barrier to entrepreneurial activity, with 55.8% of respondents indicating that fear would prevent them from starting a business (33% somewhat agree, 22.8% strongly agree). This fear appears more pronounced among women, with 57.3% expressing concern compared to 54.1% of men. The gender disparity in fear of failure might reflect different risk perceptions or varying access levels to support networks and resources. Only 18.5% of respondents indicated they would not be deterred by fear of failure (4.8% strongly disagree, 13.7% somewhat disagree), while 25.8% maintained a neutral position. The high proportion of those affected by fear of failure, combined with the challenging business environment, suggests a need for robust support systems and risk-mitigation mechanisms for aspiring entrepreneurs. This fear might be particularly acute given the additional uncertainties the ongoing conflict introduces, including physical security risks, market instability, and potential loss of assets.

Figure 5.7. Fear of Business Failure in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The overall analysis of entrepreneurial self-perceptions and affiliations in Ukraine presents a complex picture of cautious optimism tempered by significant concerns. The data suggests that while many Ukrainians possess or believe they possess entrepreneurial capabilities, they face substantial psychological and practical barriers to entrepreneurial action. The gender analysis reveals persistent differences in self-perception and risk assessment, with women generally expressing lower confidence in their capabilities and higher fear of failure despite showing similar perceptions of opportunities. These findings indicate a need for targeted interventions that address both practical skill development and psychological barriers to entrepreneurship, with particular attention to gender-specific challenges. Furthermore, the high levels of uncertainty across all dimensions suggest that strengthening the support ecosystem for entrepreneurs, including mentorship programmes, business education, and risk-sharing mechanisms, could be crucial for fostering entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine's challenging environment.

5.2.1. Problems and Needs of Veteran Entrepreneurs

The analysis of veteran entrepreneurs' challenges in Ukraine reveals a complex tapestry of business-related difficulties, with several distinct patterns emerging from the qualitative data. Financial challenges emerge as a primary concern, with respondents specifically highlighting

difficulties accessing capital and maintaining profitable operations. This financial strain appears to be exacerbated by high rental costs and tax burdens, suggesting a need for more targeted financial support mechanisms for veteran entrepreneurs.

A significant theme that emerges is the bureaucratic complexity faced by veteran entrepreneurs. Respondents frequently mentioned administrative procedures, competitive pressures, and taxation systems challenges. The data suggests that these bureaucratic hurdles may be particularly challenging for veterans transitioning from military service to entrepreneurial ventures, indicating a potential need for streamlined administrative processes specifically designed for veteran entrepreneurs.

Perhaps most notably, there appears to be a significant information gap, with respondents indicating limited access to information about legislative changes and available benefits. This finding suggests a critical need for improved communication channels and information dissemination systems tailored to veteran entrepreneurs. Responses indicating "no problems as a veteran" alongside those citing "lack of support" suggest varying experiences within the veteran entrepreneur community, possibly related to different sectors or regions.

5.2.2. Problems and Needs of Entrepreneurs with Disabilities

The analysis of challenges faced by entrepreneurs with disabilities presents a multifaceted landscape of barriers and needs. A prominent theme emerging from the data is the intersection of health-related challenges with business operations. Respondents reported various physical limitations affecting their business activities, from visual impairments to mobility issues, which directly impact their ability to maintain consistent business operations and manage traditional business requirements.

Financial accessibility emerges as a critical concern, with respondents highlighting multiple dimensions of this challenge. These include difficulties in accessing working capital, challenges securing funds for medical treatment, and limited access to humanitarian programmes or state support. The data suggests a clear need for more inclusive financial systems that consider the unique circumstances of entrepreneurs with disabilities.

Infrastructure and accessibility issues form another significant cluster of challenges. Respondents highlighted difficulties with physical mobility, particularly concerning administrative requirements and business operations. The mention of hope for implementing electronic forms (E-forms) suggests a potential solution pathway, indicating that digital transformation of administrative processes could significantly benefit entrepreneurs with disabilities.

Social and systemic barriers also feature prominently in the responses. These include communication difficulties, lack of understanding from various stakeholders, and limited access to information and services. The data reveals a complex interplay between disability-specific challenges and broader business challenges, with some respondents noting that they face "the same problems as people without disabilities," while others highlight disability-specific barriers.

The data also indicates a significant economic dimension, with respondents citing concerns about reduced customer numbers, declining purchasing power among the population, and difficulties in maintaining profitable operations. These challenges appear compounded by limited state support and bureaucratic hurdles, suggesting a need for more comprehensive support systems that address both disability-specific and general business needs.

5.3. Creating Inclusive Workplaces by Entrepreneurs

The analysis of inclusive workplace practices and support needs in Ukrainian businesses reveals significant insights into the current state of workplace diversity and inclusion efforts. This section examines companies' experiences with hiring vulnerable groups, existing inclusion policies, and required support for creating more inclusive workplaces.

The data on hiring experiences from vulnerable groups (Fig. 5.8) presents a mixed picture of inclusion efforts among Ukrainian businesses. Among companies that provided information, 35% report successful experiences in hiring employees from vulnerable groups, whilst 10.3% acknowledge unsuccessful attempts. The majority (54.7%) have no experience with such hiring practices. These figures suggest that while some businesses have made progress in inclusive hiring, there remains significant room for expansion of such practices. The relatively high success rate among those who have attempted inclusive hiring (77.3% of those with experience report success) indicates that such initiatives can be effective when properly implemented. However, more than half of businesses have no experience in this area, highlighting a significant gap in inclusive employment practices.

Hiring experiences from vulnerable groups

Figure 5.8. Hiring experiences from vulnerable groups, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Implementing formal inclusion policies demonstrates varying levels of organisational commitment to workplace diversity (Fig. 5.9.). Only 19.1% of responding businesses report having approved inclusion policies, whilst an additional 21% incorporate inclusivity principles in their corporate code of ethics. A further 13.8% maintain flexible work policies that support inclusion, though without formal documentation. However, 46.1% of businesses report having no inclusion-related policies whatsoever. This distribution suggests that while some businesses have taken concrete steps toward formalising their commitment to inclusion, the majority still operate without structured approaches to workplace diversity. The combined figure of 53.9% of businesses having some form of inclusion consideration (whether through formal policies, corporate codes, or flexible arrangements) indicates a growing awareness of the importance of workplace inclusion, albeit with varying levels of formalisation.

Implementation of inclusion policies

Figure 5.9. Implementation of inclusion policies, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The assessment of support needs for creating inclusive workplaces reveals specific areas where businesses require assistance (Fig. 5.10.). The most frequently identified need is for training and development of responsible personnel, with 37% of those requiring support identifying this as a priority. This is followed by equal emphasis (23% each) on expert support for organising inclusive spaces and company-wide training in inclusive communication. Additional assistance in developing or reviewing inclusive hiring policies was identified as necessary by 16.5% of those seeking support. When examining these needs against the total survey population, the figures demonstrate that 11.4% of all surveyed businesses seek personnel training, 7.1% require expert support for inclusive space organisation, 7% need company-wide inclusive communication training, and 5% request assistance with policy development. These proportions suggest that while the absolute numbers may appear modest, there is a clear and specific demand for various types of inclusion-related support.

Figure 5.10. Need for Assistance in Developing or Revising Inclusive Hiring Policies

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The data suggests a three-tier challenge: first, the need to expand the number of businesses actively engaging in inclusive hiring practices; second, the importance of formalising inclusion commitments through documented policies; and third, the necessity of providing targeted

support to businesses ready to enhance their inclusion efforts. The relatively high success rate among businesses that have attempted inclusive hiring suggests that with proper support and commitment, such initiatives can be successful. However, the predominance of businesses without any experience or formal policies indicates that significant work remains to be done in promoting and facilitating workplace inclusion in Ukraine's business environment. The specific support needs identified provide clear direction for policymakers and support organisations in developing targeted programmes to assist businesses in creating more inclusive workplaces.

In 2024, societal attitudes towards entrepreneurship in Ukraine reveal notable gender differences. Women generally view entrepreneurship more favorably as a career choice and associate it with higher social status, potentially influenced by media representation. Men, on the other hand, are more likely to perceive starting a business as a straightforward process. This contrast suggests that women recognize the broader value of entrepreneurship, while men focus more on its practical feasibility.

In terms of self-perception, men exhibit greater confidence in their entrepreneurial skills. Conversely, women are more optimistic about identifying opportunities but report a higher fear of failure, especially within the challenging context of ongoing war. These disparities underscore the need for tailored support programs to address the unique challenges faced by male and female entrepreneurs in Ukraine's tumultuous environment. Such efforts could promote confidence, reduce barriers, and foster a more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem

6. Entrepreneurial Aspirations

6.1. Current and Expected Employment

The analysis of employment patterns in Ukrainian enterprises during 2024 reveals a distinctive characteristic of the country's business landscape: micro-enterprises predominance, coupled with varying expectations for future development. This structure reflects both the current realities and future perspectives of businesses operating under challenging conditions.

Current employment data demonstrates that Ukrainian businesses predominantly operate on a micro scale, with 79.1% of enterprises employing between 1-10 people (Fig. 6.1.). This concentration in the micro-enterprise segment represents the foundational layer of Ukraine's business environment. A small but significant portion of businesses operate at larger scales, with 7.3% employing 11-20 people and another 7.3% employing more than 31 people. The minimal proportion of businesses without employees (3.6%) suggests that most entrepreneurial ventures actively contribute to job creation despite challenging circumstances.

Figure 6.1. Current employment vs Expected employment in 5 years

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The forward-looking perspective reveals an intriguing pattern in entrepreneurs' expectations for the next five years. While micro-enterprises continue to dominate future projections, with 67.5% expecting to employ 1-10 people, there is a notable shift in the distribution. The proportion of businesses expecting to operate without employees increases substantially to 17.5%, potentially reflecting increased uncertainty about future business conditions. The share of medium-sized businesses (11-20 employees) remains relatively stable at 7.5%, with the same percentage projecting to employ more than 31 people.

Perhaps most telling is the significant decrease in response rates between current employment (110 valid responses) and future projections (40 valid responses), accompanied by an increase in "Don't Know" responses. This marked decline in response confidence suggests considerable uncertainty about future business conditions among Ukrainian entrepreneurs. The mean employment category drops slightly from 2.31 for current employment to 2.13 for future projections, indicating a modest downward adjustment in overall employment expectations.

The pattern of predominantly micro-scale operations with cautious future outlooks appears well-adapted to the current Ukrainian context. While businesses maintain their operations and some even plan for growth, the high uncertainty about future employment projections suggests

a pragmatic approach to business planning in response to current challenges. Thus, The employment pattern reflects the resilience of Ukrainian businesses and their measured approach to future development in an uncertain environment.

6.2. Expectations for Business Growth

The analysis of business growth expectations among Ukrainian entrepreneurs in 2024 reveals significant insights into both overall trends and gender-specific patterns in perceptions of the business environment.

The data demonstrates that the largest segment of entrepreneurs anticipates stability in business conditions, with approximately 35% of both male and female entrepreneurs expecting conditions to remain "about the same as a year ago" (Fig. 6.2.). This similarity in outlook between genders suggests a shared assessment of the fundamental business environment stability. However, notable gender differences emerge when examining more optimistic and pessimistic perspectives.

Figure 6.2. Expectations for business growth in Ukraine among TEA with breakdown by gender

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Male entrepreneurs demonstrate greater optimism in their growth expectations, with 18% anticipating "somewhat higher" growth than 10% of female entrepreneurs. This gender gap in positive outlook is particularly pronounced in the moderate growth category, though both genders show similar levels (around 5%) of "much higher" growth expectations. This disparity might reflect different experiences with or access to growth opportunities between male and female entrepreneurs.

Conversely, female entrepreneurs show a more pronounced tendency toward pessimistic outlooks, with approximately 21% expecting "much lower" growth compared to 13% of their male counterparts. Both genders share similar expectations in the "somewhat lower" category (around 30%), indicating that while moderate concerns are consistent across genders, severe pessimism is more prevalent among female entrepreneurs. This pattern of higher pessimism among female entrepreneurs might reflect gender-specific challenges or barriers in the business environment.

The gender-differentiated expectations suggest a need for targeted support mechanisms that address female entrepreneurs' specific challenges, while also highlighting the importance of understanding why male entrepreneurs generally maintain more optimistic growth expectations. The overall pattern indicates that while stability is the predominant expectation across both genders, the distribution of more extreme positive and negative views shows significant gender-based variation.

6.3. Anticipations for Increased Utilization of Digital Technologies

The analysis reveals that approximately 30.6% of early-stage entrepreneurs definitely plan to increase their utilization of digital technologies for sales and service delivery in the upcoming six months. This significant proportion reflects a strategic recognition of digital transformation's importance in contemporary business operations, although it represents a decrease from the previous year's 49% positive response rate. This shift might indicate a more mature and realistic assessment of digital adoption capabilities and requirements in the current business environment.

A particularly interesting finding is the substantial proportion of entrepreneurs (24.1%) who indicated uncertainty about their digital technology adoption plans by selecting "Maybe" as their response (Fig. 6.3.). This figure, while lower than the previous year's 32%, suggests a persistent careful consideration of technological investments, possibly influenced by factors such as implementation costs, technical expertise requirements, or uncertainty about return on investment. This significant "Maybe" category highlights the complexity of digital transformation decisions in the current business landscape.

Fig. 6.3. Expectations to use more digital technologies to sell product or service in the next six months

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The data also shows that 31.5% of entrepreneurs do not plan to increase their digital technology usage, a notable increase from the previous year's 18%. This could indicate either satisfaction with current digital capabilities or the presence of business models where additional digital integration may not provide substantial benefits. The small but notable percentage (1.9%) who refused to respond and those who indicated "Don't Know" (12%) suggests some degree of uncertainty or strategic ambiguity in digital transformation planning.

This year's findings present a more nuanced picture of digital adoption intentions compared to 2023, with a more even distribution across different response categories. The shift from predominantly positive intentions to a more balanced distribution might reflect a maturing market where entrepreneurs are making more calculated decisions about digital transformation, based on their specific business needs and capabilities rather than following general digitalization trends.

In Ukraine, most entrepreneurs currently provide only a small number of jobs in the initial phase, but there is an ambition to significantly increase employment in the next five years, as evidenced by the increase in those who want to create 20 or more jobs. Entrepreneurs' expectations for business growth are cautiously optimistic, with many expecting stability and a few having high hopes for expansion. There is a clear gender gap: Men are slightly more optimistic about growth than women. In addition, almost half of early-stage entrepreneurs plan to increase their use of digital technologies, reflecting a trend towards digitalization, although women are slightly more uncertain in this regard. This trend towards digitalization, combined with the expectation of job creation, points to a potentially transformative post-war period as entrepreneurs prepare for a digital, growth-oriented future.

7. Informal investors

7.1. Rate of informal investment

An **informal investor**, as defined by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), is an individual who invests personal funds in a private company with which they have no familial or personal ties. These transactions typically occur outside the structured environments of formal venture capital or angel investment networks.

The accompanying graph analyzes the percentage of informal investors by gender in 2023 and 2024. The overall level of informal investors declined from **14% in 2023** to **13% in 2024**. Male investors accounted for **18% in 2023**, but their participation decreased to **16% in 2024**. Meanwhile, the share of women as informal investors remained stable at **10%** in both years.

These figures highlight a decline in activity among male investors, while the participation of female investors remains consistent. This trend may reflect varying influences or external factors affecting different gender groups, such as differing risk tolerance, economic conditions, or societal roles during times of crisis.

Figure. 7.1. Informal investor activity in Ukraine for period of 2021-2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

7.2. Median investment amounts for informal investors

Spectrum of Informal Investments in Ukraine in 2024. The diagram (Figure 7.2) illustrates the range of informal investments in Ukraine for 2024, as confirmed by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) Adult Population Survey. At the lower end, the smallest recorded investment is \$20, indicating that some individuals make modest financial contributions to businesses with which they have no personal ties.

The average investment amount also showed a decline, from \$1,326 in 2023 to \$1,126 in 2024, suggesting a shift in the typical contribution of informal investors. This trend may reflect changes in the entrepreneurial support ecosystem or economic factors influencing startup financing.

Fig. 7.2. Average investment amounts for informal investors, \$, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

At the higher end, investments reach up to \$5,456, demonstrating that certain informal investors possess the capacity and willingness to provide significant financial support.

This wide range of investment amounts highlights the broad participation in informal investment activities in Ukraine, with investors displaying varied levels of financial commitment in 2024. This diversity underscores the importance of informal investments in fostering entrepreneurship and supporting business development during challenging times.

Gender-Based Analysis of Informal Investment in Ukraine in 2024. According to the data analysis (Figure 7.3), informal male investors have a higher average investment amount of \$1,499, compared to informal female investors, whose average investment amount is \$1,075.

This disparity may reflect differences in available resources, risk tolerance, or investment strategies between genders. Despite the variation in average amounts, both male and female investors contribute significantly to informal investment activities, playing a crucial role in supporting entrepreneurship in Ukraine. This data highlights the need for tailored strategies to encourage and support participation across genders in informal investment activities.

Average investment amounts for informal investors, \$

Figure 7.3. Average investment amounts for informal investors by gender, \$, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

This indicates a gender disparity in the amount of investment: men invest on average about 39% more than their female counterparts. This inequality may be due to underlying factors such as differences in income levels, risk aversion or access to capital between women and men.

7.3. Relationships between investors and recipients of investments

Data from the APS indicate that in 2024, the most common type of relationship between informal investors and recipients of investments in Ukraine was "friend or neighbor," accounting for 30% of all cases (Figure 7.4). This underscores the critical role of personal relationships in informal investment activities, where trust and familiarity often play a significant role in decision-making.

Relationships between investors and the recipients of their investments in Ukraine

Figure 7.4. Relationships between investors and the recipients of their investments in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

The graph reflects changes in sources of trust for financial or business decisions in 2023 and 2024. Respondents continue to place the greatest trust in friends or neighbors, although their

share decreased slightly from **32% in 2023** to **30% in 2024**. Close relatives remain the second most trusted source, showing a slight increase from **28% to 29%**.

Notably, trust in colleagues and strangers with good business ideas increased significantly, with both categories rising from **13% to 16%**. Conversely, trust in other relatives declined from **9% to 8%**. The "Other" category also saw modest growth, increasing from **2% in 2023** to **4% in 2024**.

Overall, respondents still rely most on people from their immediate circles, such as friends, neighbors, and family members, as informal investors. However, the growing trust in colleagues and strangers with innovative business ideas indicates a gradual shift toward valuing professional connections and seeking new opportunities through less traditional channels. This shift suggests an evolving approach to business decision-making, where new relationships and innovative ideas are becoming increasingly influential.

In summary, the informal investment landscape in Ukraine in 2024 reveals a diverse range of relationships between investors and recipients. While a significant proportion of investments occur within close personal and family networks, there is also openness to supporting businesses led by colleagues and even unknown entrepreneurs with compelling business ideas.

Data from GEM Ukraine for 2024 highlight the importance of the gender aspect in investment patterns, demonstrating that women and men approach informal investing from different perspectives, often guided by social, emotional, and professional factors. This diversity underscores the evolving nature of informal investments and the growing inclusivity within Ukraine’s entrepreneurial ecosystem.

8. Ukraine National context for entrepreneurship

8.1. Expert assessment of Ukraine's entrepreneurial landscape in 2024

Through the annual National Expert Survey (NES), GEM evaluates the national business landscape. The standard procedure involves surveying at least four experts in each of the nine defined thematic areas within NES. However, given the exceptional circumstances of the ongoing war in Ukraine and the limitations in responses to the Adult Population Survey (APS), the decision was made to expand the pool of expert opinions.

In 2024, a comprehensive survey was conducted for the Ukraine GEM Report, involving 57 experts. These experts were selected based on their extensive knowledge and experience in at least one of the key framework conditions for entrepreneurship. The selection criteria included individuals in senior leadership positions, policymakers, entrepreneurs, government officials, academics, and professionals from organizations supporting entrepreneurs.

The assessment covered twelve entrepreneurial frameworks, grouped into nine thematic blocks. These frameworks encompassed various aspects, including: Entrepreneurial financing, Government policies, Support programs, Education and training, Research and development transfer, Infrastructure, Market dynamics, Physical services, Cultural norms.

The **National Entrepreneurship Context Index (NECI)**, a key component of the GEM report, serves as a comprehensive indicator assessing the vibrancy of a country's entrepreneurial ecosystem. NECI evaluates **13 Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions (EFCs)**, covering factors ranging from the availability and accessibility of financial resources to cultural and social norms supporting entrepreneurial activity. NECI combines individual scores for these conditions into a single index, providing an overarching view of the country's entrepreneurial environment.

The following sections present the findings of selected experts regarding the entrepreneurial environment in Ukraine in 2024. These insights shed light on the country's strengths and areas requiring attention to further enhance the resilience and potential of Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

8.2. National entrepreneurship framework condition in Ukraine

It is important to assess the impact of the war on the framework conditions for entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine. Let us compare the charts (Figure 8.1), which reflect the evaluation ratings for 2023 and 2024.

Comparative analysis of rating assessments indicates that the framework conditions for entrepreneurship in Ukraine in 2024 exhibit both positive dynamics and challenges.

Overall, 2024 demonstrates positive trends in areas such as access to financing, government support programs for entrepreneurs, technology transfer, and the regulatory environment. However, certain aspects, including tax policy, physical infrastructure, and entrepreneurial education in schools, require improvement to create more favorable conditions for business development.

The growth of the **Entrepreneurship Education Post-School** indicator—from 5.2 in 2023 to 5.38 in 2024—should be acknowledged as significant. Despite the war, the ecosystem shows

steady development of educational programs for entrepreneurs at the university level and through professional courses. In Ukraine's business environment, the support of international grant programs fosters the formation of entrepreneurial intellectual capital.

Fig. 8.1. Expert rating of the entrepreneurial framework conditions, 2023/2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2023/2024

In 2024, the **Research and Development Transfers** rating increased by +0.68, which may be attributed to improved collaboration between businesses and scientific institutions.

In 2024, the entrepreneurial environment in Ukraine shows signs of improvement in access to financing (**Entrepreneurial Finance**). The indicator increased to 4.17 in 2024 compared to 3.3 in 2023, indicating positive developments in financing tools for entrepreneurs. This may reflect an increase in the availability of credit programs or investments.

The **Ease of Access to Entrepreneurial Finance** also demonstrates a positive change, rising by +0.87 compared to 2023. This significant improvement suggests enhanced conditions for obtaining financing, potentially due to the digitalization of banking services or the emergence of new financial mechanisms.

In 2024, there has been some improvement in the indicators for **Government Policies: Support and Relevance** (rising from 3.2 to 3.99) and **Government Entrepreneurial Programs** (from 3.1 to 3.91). These positive changes in the evaluation of entrepreneurship conditions in Ukraine may result from the implementation of more effective programs to support entrepreneurs, aimed at fostering business development and enhancing government programs, such as grants or educational initiatives.

However, other aspects of the framework conditions in the area of government policies show signs of decline. In 2024, the ratings for **Government Policies: Taxes and Bureaucracy** and **Entrepreneurship Education at School** decreased by -0.92 and -0.77, respectively. This decline reflects a worsening situation regarding tax or bureaucratic aspects, which may be attributed to increased regulatory pressure or more complicated tax procedures. The drop in the **Entrepreneurship Education at School** indicator may indicate reduced focus on entrepreneurial education within school curricula or insufficient resources for its implementation.

Expert evaluations of entrepreneurial infrastructure in 2024 confirm a decline in the framework conditions for **Commercial and Professional Infrastructure** (-0.56), **Physical Infrastructure** (-1.43), and **Ease of Entry: Market Dynamics** (-0.31). This decrease may indicate issues with the accessibility or quality of services for businesses, such as legal support or consulting for new market entrants, as well as deteriorating access to transportation, logistics, or other physical infrastructure.

Despite significant external pressures, Ukraine's entrepreneurial ecosystem remains resilient and demonstrates the capacity for further development.

The implementation of these recommendations will not only improve the overall indicators of entrepreneurial development but also create a stable environment for long-term economic growth in Ukraine. This will contribute to the creation of new jobs, an increase in tax revenues, and the enhancement of the country's competitiveness.

8.3. The NECI: An overall view of condition for entrepreneurship

The **National Entrepreneurship Context Index (NECI)** for Ukraine in 2024 stands at **4.38**, slightly higher than in 2023 (4.3). This figure is particularly significant given two key factors: Ukraine's classification in Group C, which includes countries with a GDP per capita of less than \$25,000, and the devastating consequences of the ongoing war following Russia's invasion in 2022 (Figure 8.2). Despite these challenges, which typically have a negative impact on economic activity and the entrepreneurial climate, Ukraine demonstrates remarkable resilience and an ability to maintain a supportive environment for entrepreneurship.

Fig. 8.2. NACI of Ukraine in comparison with neighboring countries, 2024

Source: Global Report, 25 Years and Growing

Ukraine's NECI level in 2024 is comparable to that of neighboring Group B countries, such as **Poland and Romania**, which have higher GDP per capita and have not faced similar wartime

conditions. This comparison highlights Ukraine’s extraordinary achievements under difficult circumstances. For example, **Hungary**, with a slightly higher NECI score (4.5), and the **Slovak Republic**, with a lower score (4.0), operate under conditions of political stability and economic advantages linked to higher GDP per capita.

Ukraine's ability to maintain a favorable entrepreneurial ecosystem even during wartime highlights its deep fundamental strengths. Among these are effective policies, a robust educational system, and a culture that fosters entrepreneurial activity. This resilience is a testament to the country's economic durability and the strong entrepreneurial spirit of its citizens, who continue to create and grow businesses despite extraordinary pressures.

Table 8.1, which presents a differentiated analysis of Ukraine's business environment compared to neighboring countries, highlights both strengths and areas for improvement. In the area of **corporate finance**, Ukraine faces slightly less favorable conditions than some of its neighbors. This indicates that, while financial resources are available, they may be less extensive or accessible compared to countries such as **Romania** and **Hungary**.

Table 8.1 Expert assessment of the business environment in Ukraine compared to neighboring countries

Entrepreneurial Framework	Ukraine	Romania	Poland	Hungary	Slovak Rep.
A1. Entrepreneurial Finance	4,37	4.1	4.4	4.4	4.1
A2. Ease of Access to Entrepreneurial Finance	4,17	4.3	3.8	4.5	4.1
B1. Government policies: Support and Relevance	3,99	3.2	3.4	3.6	2.6
B2. Government policies: Taxes and Bureaucracy	3,48	4.3	4	5	3.8
C. Government Entrepreneurial Programs	3,91	3.8	4.4	4.3	3.2
D1. Entrepreneurship Education at School	4,43	2.7	2.2	2.2	3
D2. Entrepreneurship Education Post-School	5,38	4.5	3.1	4.3	4.2
E. Research and Development Transfers	3,98	3.8	3.5	3.9	2.8
F. Commercial and Professional Infrastructure	4,44	5.8	5.4	5.7	4.9
C1. Ease of Entry: Market Dynamics	4,59	5.2	6.6	5.2	5.6
C2. Ease of Entry: Burdens and Regulation	3,90	4.4	4.2	4.4	4.3
H. Physical infrastructure	4,77	6.2	5.9	6.4	6.6
I. Social and Cultural Norms	5,37	3.6	4.5	4.2	3.1

Source: Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2024 Global Report, 25 Years and Growing

Ukraine demonstrates a relatively favorable environment in terms of **tax policy and bureaucracy**, outperforming Romania and Poland, and significantly surpassing Hungary and Slovakia. Despite moderate indicators for government support, there is substantial potential to expand state involvement to reach or exceed the level of support seen in Romania.

Entrepreneurship-oriented education is one of Ukraine's key strengths. This is particularly evident in extracurricular learning, where the country holds a leading position in the region, second only to Hungary. This highlights a strong foundation for fostering entrepreneurial skills and mindset among the youth.

In the area of **research and development transfers** to businesses, Ukraine lags behind its neighbors. This disconnect between the academic sector and practical application may hinder the development of innovative enterprises and create barriers to their growth.

Ukraine's **commercial and professional infrastructure** is reliable but has room for improvement to reach the levels of Romania and Poland. The country's **market dynamics** remain competitive; however, the regulatory burden is average for the region, highlighting the need for further simplification of regulations.

Despite the wartime situation, Ukraine's **physical infrastructure** remains stable and is approaching the performance levels of neighboring countries such as Hungary and Slovakia. This provides a strong potential to support business processes and logistical operations.

One of Ukraine's key strengths lies in its **social and cultural norms**, which foster a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship. This unique factor distinguishes Ukraine from its neighbors. Cultural resilience serves as a critical foundation for business development and community support, particularly during wartime.

In summary, Ukraine possesses significant advantages in **education and societal attitudes toward entrepreneurship** but faces challenges in **government support** and the integration of **scientific research into business**. Comparisons with neighboring countries suggest opportunities to adopt best practices to further enhance the entrepreneurial environment. By leveraging its robust educational foundation and societal support, Ukraine can successfully overcome war-related challenges and strengthen its economic potential.

8.4. Expert comment about national conditions for entrepreneurship

The expert survey includes open-ended questions designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the key challenges and support mechanisms within the national entrepreneurial environment, as well as to formulate recommendations for its improvement.

The data presented in the chart (Figure 8.3) reflect experts' assessments of the factors influencing entrepreneurship development in Ukraine in 2024, with a particular emphasis on the effects of the war. The most influential factor, identified by **27% of respondents**, is **government policy**. In the context of the ongoing military conflict, this strong focus on government actions indicates experts' concerns about the impact of policy decisions on the business environment.

Fig. 8.3. Most fostering factor influencing the development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

In addition to government policy, **12% of experts** identified **entrepreneurial capacity** as an important driver of entrepreneurial activity. In the context of the war, given the predominantly positive nature of this factor, it is crucial to emphasize the pressing need for measures aimed at fostering a favorable entrepreneurial climate.

This underscores the importance of initiatives that enhance entrepreneurial skills, provide access to resources, and build an ecosystem that supports resilience and growth, even under challenging circumstances.

Less significant factors include the **economic climate** (4 points), **cultural and social norms** (3 points), and **financial support for entrepreneurship** (3 points). The ongoing crisis, **market openness**, and **government programs** each received 2 points, indicating their limited influence. The least significant factors are **internationalization** and the **political, institutional, and social context**, each scoring 1 point.

Overall, the data demonstrate that entrepreneurship is most heavily influenced by **government policy**. At the same time, **education support, financing**, and a **favorable social climate** remain important. Other factors, while currently less impactful, could gain greater significance under specific circumstances, highlighting the dynamic nature of the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Figure 8.4 presents expert recommendations for the development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine in 2024 against the backdrop of the ongoing war. This chart quantifies the influence of various factors on the entrepreneurial process or phenomenon. The key finding is the **significant dominance of government policies**, which hold the greatest weight among all categories. This underscores their critical role in the studied context.

Government programs and **financial support for entrepreneurship** play secondary roles, exerting noticeable influence but falling significantly behind government policies. Other factors, such as **corruption**, the **economic climate**, and the **political, institutional, and social context**, have a lesser impact, though they remain important considerations. The least impactful categories include **sustainability, social responsibility**, and **market openness**, indicating their limited role in this specific context.

Overall, the chart highlights that **government policies** are the defining factor for entrepreneurship development, while other aspects, although secondary, still contribute to shaping the ecosystem and should not be overlooked.

Fig. 8.4. Main recommendation for development of entrepreneurship in Ukraine, 2024

Source: GEM Ukraine, 2024

Other areas such as commercial and professional infrastructure, the political, institutional and social context and government programs are also mentioned, albeit with a lower weighting,

suggesting that while they are important, they may currently be overshadowed by the more critical issues of politics and corruption. In addition, the lower emphasis on education and training may reflect the need to prioritize immediate practical measures to support entrepreneurship in times of crisis over longer-term educational initiatives.

The entrepreneurial ecosystem of Ukraine in 2024 is characterized by several key factors. Improved access to financing reflects positive progress in enhancing financial mechanisms and tools aimed at supporting entrepreneurial activity. The increased efficiency of government support, driven by the implementation of programs and policies, highlights the government's active efforts to create a favorable business environment.

At the same time, declines in education indicators, physical infrastructure, and socio-cultural norms point to challenges in the long-term strategy for developing the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Tax and bureaucratic challenges remain significant obstacles, hindering the development of the business environment. The deterioration in market entry conditions underscores the need to optimize professional infrastructure and simplify access to markets.

The analysis shows that government policy is the most influential factor in shaping the entrepreneurial ecosystem, carrying the greatest weight in the study and confirming its critical role. Government programs and financial support rank second in influence. While less significant than government policies, they still have a noticeable impact on fostering entrepreneurship in Ukraine.
